

Evolving energy systems in maritime transport: A parameter analysis for hydrogen fueled combined cycle gas turbine

MARPOWER project

Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT

Master's Program in Sustainable Energy Systems, Energy Technology

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ABSTRACT

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Keywords: MARPOWER project, gas turbine, waste heat boiler, hydrogen, maritime transport, energy system, PPTD

Climate change is pressuring the marine transportation sector to cut down emissions and fast, starting with 2% in year 2025. The Maritime sector has an important role in the global economies since it is used for exporting goods and transporting people and the sector is only expected to grow. As regulations are set to mitigate emissions, renewable energy sources bring the solution to fueling the sector in the future. Hydrogen properties have made it stand out as the fuel of the future in for marine engines, especially in gas turbines. Combining hydrogen with combined cycle gas turbine optimizes the fuel usage and efficiency of the system.

This master's thesis is done under the EU-funded MARPOWER project. The project aims to bring a combined gas turbine power system to maritime usage that can flexibly use the alternative fuels, including hydrogen. The aim was to see in what state the studies regarding gas turbines in marine sector are and analyze the gas turbine process with two cases that had different TITs. Parameter optimization of the combined cycle gas turbine shows the dependencies of seawater temperature and waste heat recovery boiler's PPTD on other parameters. With set boundary conditions, a higher turbine inlet temperature results in lower boiler outlet temperature for exhaust gas and higher efficiency. The rising temperature of the seawater used in an intercooler as well as the increase of the PPTD effect negatively on the net electric efficiency. Higher turbine inlet temperature shows increasing ability to convey heat to the steam side in a WHRB to generate electricity. The efficiency of a gas turbine cycle can be improved by adding a WHRS to fully utilize the heat from the exhaust gas. The improvement in net electric efficiency can be over 4 percentage points.

TIIVISTELMÄ

Lappeenrannan–Lahden teknillinen yliopisto LUT

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Satu Lehto

Meriliikenteen kehittyvät energiajärjestelmät: Parametritarkastelu vedyllä toimivalle kombiprosessille

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Ilmastonmuutos pakottaa meriliikenteen vähentämään päästöjä nopeasti, alkaen 2 %:n vähennyksellä vuonna 2025. Merenkulkusektorilla on tärkeä rooli maailman talouksissa, sillä sitä käytetään tavarankuljetukseen ja ihmisten kuljetukseen, ja sektorin odotetaan vain kasvavan. Kun päästöjä rajoittavia säädöksiä otetaan käyttöön, uusiutuvat energialähteet tarjoavat ratkaisun alan tulevaisuuden polttoaineeksi. Vedyn ominaisuudet ovat tehneet siitä tulevaisuuden polttoaineen laivojen moottoreissa, erityisesti kaasuturbiineissa. Vedyn yhdistäminen yhdistettyyn kaasuturbiiniin optimoi polttoaineen käytön ja järjestelmän tehokkuuden.

Tämä diplomityö on tehty EU-rahoitteisen MARPOWER-hankkeen puitteissa. Hankkeen tavoitteena on tuoda kombiprosessi merikäyttöön, joka voi joustavasti hyödyntää vaihtoehtoisia polttoaineita, mukaan lukien vetyä. Tavoitteena oli selvittää, missä vaiheessa merialan kaasuturbiinitekniikat ovat, sekä analysoida kaasuturbiiniprosessia kahdella eri turbiinin sisäänmenolämpötilalla. Kombiprosessin parametrioimintaa osoittaa meriveden lämpötilan sekä pinch point lämpötilaeron vaikutuksen jätelämpökattilan muihin parametreihin. Määritetyillä reunaehdoilla korkeampi turbiinin sisäänmenolämpötila johtaa pakokaasun alempaan kattilan ulostulolämpötilaan ja korkeampaan hyötysuhteeseen. Välijäähdyttimessä käytettävän meriveden lämpötilan sekä pinch point lämpötilaeron kasvu vaikuttavat negatiivisesti nettosähköhyötysuhteeseen. Korkeampi turbiinin sisäänmenolämpötila osoittaa parempaa kykyä siirtää lämpöä jätelämpökattilassa

pakokaasulta höyrypuolelle. Kaasuturbiiniprosessin tehokkuutta voidaan parantaa lisäämällä jätelämmön talteenottojärjestelmä, joka hyödyntää täysin pakokaasujen lämpöä. Sen avulla nettosähkötehokkuuden parannus voi olla yli 4 prosenttiyksikköä.

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These 5 years of university have been quite the journey. It holds the Covid-19 pandemic, countless late-night studies but also incredible student events and an unforgettable exchange. Now I can put my not-so-white overalls away and proudly say, I did it!

In Lappeenranta 30.6.2025

Satu Lehto

DECLARATION OF AI USAGE

Scopus AI has been used to find references. The references have been checked and only ones proven to be correct have been used. Microsoft Copilot has been used to help with structuring of the thesis.

SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Roman characters

p	pressure	[bar, Pa]
T	temperature	[°C, K]
qm	mass flow rate	[kg/s]
A	area	[m ²]
P	power	[W]
Q	heat rate	[W]
k	step	[°C, K]
U	overall HTC	[W/m ² K]
F	LMTD correction factor	[-]

Greek characters

θ	temperature difference	[°C, K]
Φ	heat	[kW]
ε	degree of recuperation	[-]
η	efficiency	[%]

Subscripts

a	air
approach	approach temperature
B	boiler
el	electric

eg	exhaust gas
fuel	fuel
in	inflow
LMTD	log mean temperature difference
max	maximum
n	n's value
net	net value
out	outflow
s	steam
target	target
w	water

Superscripts

'	derivative
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Abbreviations

ADP	Acid dew point
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CH ₄	Methane
CII	Carbon Intensity Indicator
CNG	Compressed natural gas
CO ₂	Carbon monoxide
CODAG	Combined diesel and gas
COGAS	Combined gas and steam

EC	European Commission
EEDI	Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index
EMSA	European Marine Safety Agency
EU	European Union
FC	Fuel cell
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GT	Gas turbine
H ₂	Hydrogen
H ₂ O	Water
HFO	Heavy fuel oil
HHV	Higher heating value
HP	high pressure
HRSG	Heat recovery system generator
HTPEMFC	High temperature polymer electrolyte fuel cell
ICE	Internal combustion engine
IMO	International Marine Organization
IPPC	Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control
LFO	Light Fuel oil
LHV	Lower heating value
LNG	Liquified Natural Gas
LOHC	Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carrier
LP	Low pressure
MDO	Marine Diesel Oil
MMT	Million metric ton

N2	Nitrogen monoxide
N2O	Nitrous oxide
NG	Natural gas
NH3	Ammonia
NOx	Nitrogen oxides
O2	Oxygen
OPS	Onshore power supply
PCC	Post combustion carbon capture
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMR	Steam methane reforming
SOx	Sulfur oxides
ST	Steam turbine
RNG	Renewable natural gas
TIT	Turbine inlet temperature
PPTD	Pinch point temperature difference
WHB	Waste heat boiler
WHR	Waste heat recovery
WHRS	Waste heat recovery system
WtW	Well-to-Wake

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1. Introduction

In 2018, around 2.9% of global human caused CO₂ emissions were created by the shipping sector. Maritime industry has become a crucial part of global economies and provides an energy-efficient mode of transportation. However, the industry relies heavily on traditional marine fuels that are the root cause of emissions. Measures to mitigate the emissions from waterborne vessels globally are needed to support the Paris Agreement adopted in COP21. The objective of Paris Agreement is to limit the global warming to well below 2°C, preferably to 1.5°C. To reach this goal, the GHG emissions in marine sector must be brought under control or the emissions could elevate 130% from the 2008 emission level of 794 million tons by 2050. (European Commission a, n.d.)

Expected growth of the sector puts pressure on finding more sustainable solutions to power waterborne vessels. In 2023 an emission reduction strategy was released by the International Maritime Organization. The aim of International Maritime Organization is for 2050 to have 70% reduction in the carbon intensity of the emissions (European Commission a, n.d.). The MARPOWER project contributes to these set requirements by implementing an advanced gas turbine system as the prime mover that runs on alternative fuels (European Commission, 2024). As we move more towards the net zero goals in the energy sector and the pollution in the shipping sector takes place in heavily populated areas such as ports, this topic is important and so is the research coming with it. Sustainable and carbon neutral fuels like hydrogen are needed for waterborne applications. This means that the machinery that comes with it needs to be able to run on these fuels. (MARPOWER, 2025)

Previous research shows that in the future the majority of investments is focused on gas turbines that are only partly fueled with hydrogen (Öberg et al., 2021). Studies done about 100% hydrogen fueled gas turbines used in maritime transportation are still limited. In 2024 Barsi et al. (2024) published an article about their study on marine gas turbine. While they talked about using hydrogen to fuel the gas turbine solely on its own or only partly, hydrogen wasn't used as a fuel in their case. Companies like Siemens have invested in commercializing hydrogen gas turbines, but their promise is to run their gas turbines with 100% hydrogen by the year 2030 (Siemens Energy, 2025). Contributing research to fully

hydrogen fueled gas turbines is important since gas turbines beat the popular internal combustion engine in many categories like sizing and noise pollution. (Baldi et al., 2022)

This master's thesis is done under the MARPOWER projects where LUT is one of the eleven collaborative partners. MARPOWER is an EU-funded project where the goal is to contribute to pioneering a pathway to decarbonize the shipping sector. The focus is on developing a flexible energy conversion system that contributes to the global efforts of fueling the maritime industry with sustainable, alternative fuel. (MARPOWER, 2025)

1.1. Research objectives

The goal of this thesis is to analyze the parameters of the gas turbine and waste heat recovery system and see if better efficiency is possible to achieve. The main parameter to analyze is the pinch point temperature difference. To validate the calculations, literature from previous research is used. This thesis does not include economic calculations which gives limitation to the result section. The goal of this thesis is summarized in five questions:

- What would be the optimal pinch point temperature difference for different boiler outlet temperatures?
- How does pinch point temperature difference affect the other components of the combined cycle?
- Is it possible to find a higher efficiency?
- What is the state of hydrogen fueled gas turbines today?
- What does it require from the gas turbine to use hydrogen as a fuel?

1.2. Structure of the thesis

On top of the introduction, this thesis consists of seven chapters that include the literature review, research on recent studies and optimization of the parameters for the hydrogen fueled combined gas turbine.

- **Chapter 2: Overview of maritime sector prime movers** sets the base for understanding the prime movers in the marine industry. The focus is on the gas turbine and its major and auxiliary components.
- **Chapter 3: Emissions and regulations** presents the currently used marine fuels and the emissions they emit. The regulators of the sector are presented as well as how they guide the sector to reach a more sustainable status. Alternative fuels such as hydrogen are discussed.
- **Chapter 4: State of hydrogen fueled gas turbines** discusses what state the industry is at the moment, which companies have manufactured gas turbines working with hydrogen and what percentage of hydrogen do they work on. On top of this, the state of recent studies and their results are analyzed.
- **Chapter 5: MARPOWER Project** discusses the MARPOWER Project and its goals. The cycle of the project is visualized and hydrogens effects on the gas turbine design are presented.
- **Chapter 6: Design parameter calculation methods** delivers the formulas and boundaries for the calculations.
- **Chapter 7: Results** addresses the values gotten from the calculation based on chapter 6. The results are visualized and compared.
- **Chapter 8: Conclusions** summarizes the results and key findings of the thesis.

2. Overview of the maritime sector prime movers

Maritime sector is very diverse and a crucial part of global trading. Even though the sector is not the biggest polluter on the global scale, but since it is expected to grow, and the pollutants are released into populated areas it's important to make changes to more sustainable alternatives (Baldi et al., 2022, 6-43). The gas turbine technology has upgraded as the interest in gas turbines in marine vessels has grown. New regulations and legislations have been set to mitigate the emissions, and the focus is shifting to the alternative fuels that help to achieve decarbonization in this heavily fossil fuel-oriented industry.

For better understanding of the marine industry and energy systems in the industry this chapter introduces the prime movers in the maritime sector as well as states their current situation and popularity in the shipping sector before diving deeper on the gas turbine and its components. After specifying the components of the gas turbine, the auxiliary devices are introduced as well since they play an important role in improving efficiency.

2.1. Energy systems in shipping sector

The main requirements of the ship's energy system are to provide mechanical, electrical and thermal power. Mechanical power is needed for the propulsion and electrical and thermal power is needed for auxiliary devices and on-board services (Baldi et al., 2022, 27). Main characteristics for the energy system are low fuel consumption and safety. The high level of safety of ship's energy systems is required by multiple certification bodies, national and international. (Baldi et al., 2022, 28)

According to Baldi et al. (2022), the prime mover for marine propulsion can be a steam turbine (ST) with relative Rankine cycle components, a gas turbine (GT) or a reciprocating internal combustion engine that is normally operating according to the Diesel cycle. Before the 1980's STs were the main type of engine used on ships. In the 80's diesel engines took first place due to the development of the diesel engine and the oil crisis. ST propulsion has its other weaknesses too that made the transition to diesel engines reasonable. When comparing the two, it's shown that ST propulsion plants have worse efficiency than the same

size diesel engines, steam circuit and generators are bulky, the rotational speeds of turbines (thousands of rpm) and the ship's propellers (around 100 rpm) are not compatible so expensive and bulky speed reducers are needed and reversing requires auxiliary turbine for fixed pitch propellers (Baldi et al., 2022, 33). Internal combustion engines (ICE) have a leading role in the global merchant fleet, nearly 98 % have it as a prime mover. Low price of heavy fuel oil (HFO) makes using ICEs economically interesting. (Mallouppas & Yfantis, 2021).

Due to the 1970's oil crises fuel cells (FC) gained more attention and interest in maritime application as a clean energy technology solution (Baldi et al., 2022, 81). To this day the main factor driving the fuel cells application on vessels is to cut down the emissions. Fuel cells have been proven to work on multiple applications on land such as transportation, but on-board applications come with new challenges. The requirements and challenges for maritime application compared to automobiles can be shortened into four concerns: operational environment, size, emissions and economic consideration. From environmental challenges the number one is fueling. Automobiles are easy to fuel on land but on sea the long voyages don't offer this option. The salty seawater is also a challenging environment because of seawater corrosion and unpredictable weather. The size of the vessels presents a related problem with fueling. Marine vessels are large so being able to fuel the whole ship with fuel cells is a challenge. Emission wise, it is important to focus on vessels since the individual emissions are more outstanding. From an economic point of view, ships have a longer lifespan when compared to automobiles but require distinct economic considerations. (Wang, 2023)

Most promising fuel cell technologies for maritime applications are PEMFC and SOFC. These fuel cells have been used in multiple marine applications on their own or with batteries. The problem today is that they are only capable of producing power up to few megawatts. This limits the exploitation of FCs to vessels voyaging short distances. On larger vessels fuel cells are still only capable of auxiliary power. (Elkafas et al., 2023)

Due to strong development of gas turbines (GT) and growing demand in propulsion systems with high power concentration on top of low polluting emissions, it reappeared in maritime transportation at the end of 1990. GT was used before but the oil crisis in 1970's blocked its use. Gas turbines have advantages over steam turbines and diesel engines. GT has smaller dimensions and is lighter. This is due to the smaller number of auxiliary devices and simpler

plant installation. GTs are reliable and can reach the maximum load in less than 5 minutes. It would take a Diesel engine to reach its maximum load about 20 minutes, and a ST would take even longer, up to 4 hours (Baldi et al., 2022, 34). If GT and ICE are compared back-to-back GT takes the win in many categories other than the starting time. When the gas turbine is the main engine the noise, vibration, maintenance intervals and the amount of lubricant oil needed reduces. (Barsi et al., 2024)

2.2. Gas turbine technology

Gas turbines can be divided into two categories: simple gas turbine and generative gas turbine. Both designs work on open and closed cycles, but popularity is leaning towards the open cycle. In the open cycle the air is constantly being drawn into the compressor and in closed-cycle the exhaust gas is recirculated. The major difference between the two gas turbine categories is that in generative gas turbine the heat from the exhaust gas is used to pre-heat the air before it enters the compressor. This way potential losses are avoided. The gas turbine cycle can be turned into a combined cycle by adding a heat recovery steam generator (HRSG). This bottoming cycle takes the exhaust gas and uses the heat from it to vaporize water to produce more energy via steam turbine. (Li et al., 2021)

Gas turbine's major components are compressor, combustor and turbine. These three parts can be seen clearly in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Gas turbine (Donev et al., 2024)

First the air enters the compressor where it is compressed to a higher pressure. No external heat is added to the air, but compression increases the air's temperature. Compressors can be divided into three categories: the positive placement compressors for low flow and high pressure, centrifugal-flow compressors for medium flow and pressure and axial-flow compressors for high flow and low pressure. Most of the compressors used in gas turbines are axial-flow compressors. (Boyce, 2012, 51)

An axial-flow compressor has multiple stages. One stage is made of a rotor and a stator. In the rotor blades the air is accelerated and after that diffused in the stator blades. The diffusion has to happen since then the gained velocity in the rotor is converted to pressure increase. Each state increases the pressure slightly. For better control, additional fixed blades can be added to the compressor inlet for making sure the air enters in the right angle. Additional diffuser can also be added to the exit of the compressor. This way it is easier to control the velocity of the air at the end. (Boyce, 2012, 54-55)

As axial-flow compressors are popular on large scale gas turbines, centrifugal-flow compressors are used in small scale gas turbines. Centrifugal compressors are known for large tolerance of process fluctuation and high reliability when compared with other compressors. The centrifugal compressor conducts an impeller, and the fluid is forced through it by rotating impeller blades. Centrifugal compressors also have diffusers that conduct of vanes. The vanes are tangential to the impeller and the velocity of the fluid is converted to pressure. (Boyce, 2012, 55-56)

There are small gas turbines that operate with both axial and centrifugal compressors. In Figure 2 the difference can be seen. The difference between the exiting fluid flow is easy to visualize from the figure. For axial compressor the fluid enters and exits in axial flow but for centrifugal compressor the fluid enters in axial flow but exits in radial flow to enter the combustor.

Figure 2. Small gas turbine (Boyce, 2012, 54)

After the fluid exits the compressor, it enters the combustor. There the air is mixed with the fuel. The pressure remains almost constant throughout the combustion phase. High temperatures are reached in the combustor which results in gaseous form of the fuel mix. The hot combustion mixture enters the turbine section. (Poullikkas, 2004).

The three major designs for combustors are tubular, tubo-annular and annular. Despite the design, all the combustors have the same features: a recirculation zone, a burning zone and a dilution zone. In the recirculation zone the fuel is evaporated, partly burnt and prepared for the combustion. At the end of the burning zone the fuel should be burnt so that in the final dilution zone the hot gas can be mixed with the dilution air. After the compressor, the mixture enters the turbine (Boyce, 2011, 387). Depending on the usage of the system, turbines are designed to be single-shaft or two-shaft. The difference between the two is that in two-shaft turbine there are two turbines back-to-back: high-pressure and low-pressure. In the maritime sector the ships have to move at a variety of speeds at ports thus implementing the two-shaft turbine is more convenient. (Fatsis, 2019)

The turbine section of the GT can have two options, either an axial-flow turbine or a radial-flow turbine. Just like the compressor, also turbines are more often axial turbines. The axial-flow turbine is used in 95% of gas turbines. With axial turbine the flow enters and leaves in the axial direction. (Boyce, 2012, 76-81)

The turbine needs to bear high temperatures because that way the efficiency can be enhanced. Higher temperatures flow through the turbine, the blades are put under enormous thermal stress, and this can cause thermal deformation. (Kim et al., 2024) The blades have a coating that ensures protection in these high temperatures. The coating can act also as a sacrificial layer that can be stripped and recoated. Life of the coating varies from 10 to 15 years. (Boyce, 2012, 49). To ensure the long lifetime of the blades, blade cooling needs to be integrated to the system. Cooling can be divided into surface film and blade internal cooling. Typically, the cooling air is taken from the compressor, but other options are available too. (Kim et al., 2024)

The best way to describe the working principle of the whole gas turbine is by the Brayton Cycle (Giampaolo, 2014, 45). Figures 3 show pressure-temperature map for gas turbine.

Figure 3. Brayton cycle pressure-temperature map

The map in Figure 3 shows that from point a to b the air is compressed in the compressor. Temperature increases a little bit, but pressure growth is more noticeable. From b to c the air enters the combustor, and the process is isobaric, so the pressure remains unchanged. The temperature grows as it is predicted. Expansion takes place from point c to d. Here the gas enters the turbine and the gas expands.

2.3. Additional components for complex cycles

Additional system components for maritime shipping systems can include heat exchangers such as recuperator or intercooler. Waste heat recovery system (WHRS) can increase the efficiency of the cycle by cutting down fuel intake needed.

2.3.1. Recuperator technology

Recuperator can be categorized as a major gas turbine component but is not a necessary part of the gas turbine. Figures 4 and 5 present a gas turbine with a recuperator.

Figure 4. Gas turbine with recuperator (Boyce, 2012. s. 41)

Figure 5. Air flow in a gas turbine with recuperator (Boyce, 2012. s. 42)

In some cases, the exhaust gas exiting the turbine can be significantly higher than the temperature of the air that enters the combustor. In a situation like this, it is more efficient for the fuel consumption to utilize the heat to preheat the compressed air entering the burning chamber. Including a recuperator to the gas turbine is possible with relatively small pressure ratios or high turbine inlet temperature (TIT). The purpose of adding a recuperator to the system is to increase the efficiency. (Poullikkas, 2004)

As seen in the figure above the intake air goes through the compressor first, then into recuperator and then into the combustor. Recuperator's purpose is to increase the efficiency of the process. Recuperator is a heat exchanger that conveys energy from a hot exhaust gas leaving the turbine to compressed air about to enter the combustor. This reduces fuel consumption of the gas turbine and increases electrical efficiency (Xiao et al., 2017). The air entering the turbine is usually above 1200 °C. (Boyce, 2012, 41)

Recuperators are divided into three different categories based on the geometry of the heat transfer surface. The three categories are primary-surface, plate-fin and tubular recuperators (Xiao et al., 2017). Figure 6 shows three types of primary-surface recuperators.

Figure 6. Types of primary surface recuperators (Xiao et al., 2017)

The primary surface recuperator is a counter-flow heat exchanger. The material is stainless steel. The recuperator is composed of multiple layers stacked on top of one another. One layer has an upper and lower sheet. The metal sheets shown in the figure are welded at the edges leaving an opening for air to enter and exit. The hot exhaust gas follows the patterns of the surface and the air flows between the two sheets. (Xiao et al., 2017)

Figure 7 shows the structure of plate-fin recuperator.

Figure 7. Plate-fin recuperator (Xiao et al., 2017)

This design forms a strong unit of plates, fins, headering bars and manifolds. The gas fin segment has a pattern that the air uses as the heat exchange surface. The exhaust gas enters in a cross-flow to the air flow. The parting plates separate the exhaust gas and air flow. (Xiao et al., 2021)

Figure 8. Tubular recuperator (Xiao et al., 2017)

Tubular recuperators consist of multiple tubes where the compressed air flows. Outside of the tubes are heated with exhaust gas. The advantages include high resistance to thermal gradient. The tubular recuperator is heavy thus it has a big impact on the total system. (Xiao et al., 2017)

An important parameter in recuperators is the degree of recuperation. The degree of recuperation represents the ratio between recuperated heat and waste heat. Degree of recuperation can be calculated as in Equation 1.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta T_{\max}}{\theta} \quad (1)$$

In the equation ε is the degree of recuperation, ΔT_{\max} is the temperature difference between outlet and inlet temperatures of the recovered fluid and θ is the difference between the inlet temperature of the heat source and inlet temperature of the recovered fluid.

Degree of recuperation works as the criteria for recuperators efficiency. It tells how much heat is possible to recover from theoretical maximum. Energy efficiency is at its highest when ΔT_{\max} is as high as possible. The size of the heat exchanger surfaces, and the cleanliness of the surface affect the efficiency of heat exchange between the two vapors. (Motiva, n.d.)

2.3.2. Intercooler technology

Intercoolers are divided to air-to-air and air-to-liquid intercoolers. In marine engines it is more common to use an air-to-liquid intercooler since water is easily accessible due to the environment. The seawater causes easily corrosion so freshwater would be more favorable to use. The seawater wouldn't only affect the intercooler but also pumps that pump the salty water on board. (Theotokatos et al., 2016)

With intercoolers, adding a regenerator such as recuperator before combustor in a gas turbine cycle is crucial for the thermal efficiency and to achieve the set turbine inlet temperature. The advantage that the intercooler gives to the system is that it lowers the amount of power that the compressor would absorb. Compressing cold air takes less power than compressing hot air. This increases the power output of the gas turbine (Beck et al., 1999, 55). Other benefits include lower thermal load to the engine and lower NO_x emissions. (Mollenhauer & Tschöke, 2010, 48)

2.3.3. Waste heat recovery system

Starting from the 1st of January in 2023, it became mandatory for every vessel to calculate their Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEDI) and Carbon Intensity Indicator (CII). These are implemented to International Maritime Organization's (IMO) strategy. As the efficiency of the process and emission reductions are top priorities in the shipping sector, the actions should be lined with them. Implementing a waste heat recovery system on-board answers these demands. (Díaz-Secades, 2023)

WHRS's aim is to take the excess heat from the primary power generation and convert to energy (Erixno, 2021). The waste heat can be classified as high, medium or low quality. The temperature range for low quality heat is 232 °C or lower. For medium quality the temperature range is 232-649 °C and for high quality 650 °C or higher. According to Singh & Pedersen (2016) waste heat in ships usually lies between low and medium quality. Utilizing this heat makes the technology an energy-efficient one that helps with fuel savings (Wang, 2023). With WHRS the demand for propulsion or auxiliary services can be met

without additional fuel consumption. As WHRS saves on fuel usage it also mitigates the emissions. (Baldi et al., 2022)

There are multiple devices to meet possible auxiliary heat demand with the waste heat in ships: recuperator, waste heat boiler, economizer, regenerator and heat recovery steam generator. Waste heat boiler (WHB) consists of tubes that are placed parallel to each other. The water gets heated by the waste heat gas and turns into vapor. It is possible to couple the WHB with other waste heat recovery technologies such as preheater or after-burners. By doing so the total efficiency of the systems achieves better efficiency. Including multiple heat recovery systems such as economizer, evaporator, superheater and steam drum make a more complex system called a heat recovery steam generator (HRSG). On top of these equipment the system includes familiar power generation plant devices: steam turbine, feedwater tank, condenser and feed water pump. Using HRSG for steam production can get system efficiency up to 85 %. (Baldi et al., 2022)

Figure 9. Heat recovery steam generator

The exhaust gas moves in the opposite direction of the water. The first heat transfer happens in the superheater as the steam needs to be dry before entering the turbine. The HRSG works on Rankine cycle and is referred as the bottoming or lower cycle. It is possible to have multiple pressure levels in the system.

The typical fuels for marine vessel prime movers are liquid fossil fuels such as Light Diesel Oil (LDO), Marine Diesel Oil (MDO) and Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO). These liquid fossil fuels create a problem with waste heat recovery (WHR) and environment with their sulfur content. The WHR requires that the exhaust gases are cooled but the temperature of the gases must be higher than acid dew point value or else it will cause corrosion. Environmentally, sulfur emissions create a huge problem and fuels containing it should be avoided or SO_x abatement devices need to be adapted to the system while using these polluting fuels (Baldi et al., 2022, 33). Alternative fuels such as hydrogen don't have this problem so implementing a HRSG system to hydrogen fueled gas turbine is possible.

2.4. Comparison of the different gas turbine cycles

Figure 10 presents the study done by Goswami and Kreith (2019). In the figure, multiple different gas turbine cycles were compared in terms of efficiency. The numbers on each curve express the pressure ratio. The TIT of 2700 °F converts to 1482.2 °C.

Figure 10. Comparison of different cycles (Goswami & Kreith, 2019, 219)

The importance of recuperator on increasing the efficiency is easily seen from the figure. Recuperated cycles are able to reach much higher efficiency right from the start. The increase

between the simple cycle and recuperated cycle is almost 20 %pt. When comparing simple cycle and intercooled cycle, the simple cycle reaches the same efficiencies than intercooled cycle with lower pressure ratio. This is up to the pressure ratio of 30. After that intercooled cycle shows higher efficiencies whereas in simple cycle the efficiency doesn't change remarkably between the pressure ratio of 30 and 40. On the cycles without recuperation, the higher the pressure ratio, the higher the efficiency. With recuperated cycles it is the opposite. Among the recuperated cycles, the highest efficiency is achieved with pressure ratios between 8 and 15.

3. Emissions and regulators

This chapter introduces the marine fossil fuels that are dominating the industry and presents the emission mitigations that are possible to achieve with the more sustainable alternatives. Marine sector is observed by several parties and the first emission reductions goals are set for the year 2025. Not only is the change of fuels in action to meet the sustainability goals but also adding carbon capture and storage technology is on its way.

3.1. Emissions

Maritime transportation produces relatively low amounts of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In EU in 2021 the emissions from maritime transportation were 3 to 4 % of total GHG or over 124 million tons of CO₂ (European Commission a, n.d.). Figure 11 shows the emissions globally in the shipping sector from the year 1970 to 2023.

Figure 11. CO₂ emissions in shipping sector 1970-2023 (Statista, 2024)

The figure shows a growth of emissions from the year 1983 until 2023. In 2019 the emissions were already plummeting but due to Covid-19 pandemic, emissions in marine shipping sector dropped significantly in 2020 as can be seen from Figure 13 (Deng & Mi, 2023). The

economy started to recover again in 2021, and emissions have grown back to the level of 2018 and overall, emissions have doubled from 1970. Maritime transportation emissions cover about 10 % of the emissions in the transportation sector. (Statista, 2024)

In Europe, emissions and their reduction have been taken seriously. The European Commission (EC) launched Fit for 55 legislative package in 2021, and it includes the FuelEU Maritime Regulation, emission reduction being the top priority (European Commission b, n.d). The FuelEU Maritime Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2023/1805) advocates for usage of renewable and low-carbon fuels on top of clean energy technologies for ships. The regulation was fully applied on the 1st of January in 2025. The key facts of Fuel EU Maritime Regulation include limits for GHG intensity of the energy used on ships, which are visualized in Figure 12, reduction of air pollution in ports and operators' freedom of choosing fuels and technologies to support the first two statements. (European Commission b, n.d.)

Figure 12. Emission reduction limits (European Commission, b, n.d.)

The reduction limit of GHG emissions is set for vessels weighting over 5000 gross tons. This concludes to 55% of all the ships and this percentage forms 90% of the CO₂ emissions in the sector. Figure 12 presents the rate of how quickly these ships in the marine sector need to decrease their emissions. These numbers don't only include carbon dioxide but also nitrous oxide and methane emissions over the full well-to-wake (WtW) cycle of the fuels used on the ship. In 2025 the GHG intensity of the fuels should be down by 2% and by the year 2050 it needs to be down by 80%. (Regulation (EU) 2023/1805, 2023)

One of the main reasons for the haste in powering the ships with zero-emission fuels is the emissions that get released on heavily populated areas such as ports. FuelEU Maritime Regulation obligates to use onshore power supply (OPS) or a zero-emission technology on ships at quayside for both berth and moored vessels starting from the 1st of January in 2030. (European Commission b, n.d.)

As stated, the maritime sector is determined to abate the emissions released into the atmosphere quickly. In addition to changing the fuels for renewable ones, there are other options as well. Post combustion carbon capture (PCC) has been proven to work on onshore power plant applications so it is possible to integrate this technology for it to work on marine vessels (Wärtsilä a, 2025). As the vessels have very limited space due to their working environment being the sea, mass, safety and economic feasibility on top of space limitations have been restrictive factors to hinder the more large-scale adaptation. (Baldi et al., 2022, 63)

While the future fuels of the marine sector are being developed, the sector can still move towards the set sustainable goals. After a successful carbon capture and storage (CCS) pilot, Wärtsilä will bring their CCS solution for shipping purposes to the market in the year of 2025. Implementing CCS solution lines up with International Maritime Organization's targets to decarbonize the maritime sector. (Wärtsilä a, 2025)

3.2. Regulators in the marine sector

International Maritime Organization IMO is the United Nations specialized agency that is responsible for safety and security of shipping sector. Prevention of marine and atmospheric pollution caused by shipping is also IMO's responsibility. (IMO a, n.d.)

IMO adopted a greenhouse gas emissions reduction strategy in 2018. The goal is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and reach a goal of zero net emissions in the maritime transportation field. In 2023 IMO adopted 2023 IMO Strategy on Reduction of GHG Emissions from Ships that includes follow-up actions to 2018 Initial strategy. The goal in the 2023 IMO GHG Strategy is to reduce the emissions internationally by at least 40 % by the year 2030 (IMOa, n.d.). One of the biggest changes that the 2023 strategy brings can be seen in the levels of ambition. In 2018 there was three levels, and the last one is called "GHG

emissions from international shipping to peak and decline”. Here, the goal was to reduce GHG emissions by 50 % by the year 2050 (IMO b, n.d.). In the new strategy from 2023 there are four levels of ambitions, and the last one is called “GHG emissions for international shipping reaching net zero”. In this level, the new goal for emissions is to reach net-zero by the year 2050. (Annex 15 MEPC 80/17 Add.1, page 6)

As mentioned earlier, the European Union and more specifically the European Commission has set regulations and directives for the maritime sector. The European Commission has set up a European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) in the early 2000’s. EMSA’s intention is to assist the EC in the fields of maritime safety, maritime security and the prevention of pollution as well as to response to pollution caused by ships. The Agency doesn’t only assist the Member States but also EU neighboring countries (European Commission c, n.d.). The EC and IMO work together to decarbonize the maritime transportation. In July 2023 the Commission welcomed the new climate ambitions by IMO and the parties together ensure that the shipping sector makes a fair contribution to attain the Paris Agreement targets. (European Commission, 2023)

3.3. Maritime fuels: energy carriers and primary energy sources

The eventual aim for marine sector and energy systems needed for operation is to be carbon neutral. For shipping industry, achieving this goal means that the industry must have zero environmental impact and must operate by using renewable energy sources (Baldi et al., 2022, 58). The majority of used fuels in the past years are fossil fuels. This can be seen from Figure 13.

Figure 13. Quantity of marine fuels in the years 2019 and 2020 (Statista, 2023)

The unit for the quantity of the fuel, MMT, stands for million metric tons. One MMT equals 1 000 000 000 kilograms. As seen from the figure above, there are differences between fuel types in both years. The clearest difference can be seen with Light Fuel Oil (LFO). In the year 2019, 6.5 MMT of LFO was used in the marine sector. In one year, its usage grew 10 times, ending up being 65.5 MMT. Even though LNG is the best choice environmentally out of all four fuels, it is also the least used one. To meet the regulations set by the EU and IMO, the usage of renewable and environmentally friendly fuels needs to take its place in the industry.

As seen in Figure 12 the first emission mitigation goals are set for this year, the year of 2025. This pushes the industry by force towards alternative fuels. Alternative options for liquid fossil fuels would include hydrogen, ammonia, methane and natural gas, and methanol. (Baldi et al., 2022, 59-65)

3.3.1. Hydrogen

Hydrogen, as a fuel, has a big impact on pushing the greener future of energy production closer to the Sustainable Development Goals (Le et al., 2023). That is why it is relevant to explore its suitability for maritime on-board purposes and weight the possible limitations. Hydrogen is the most abundant element on the Earth and in the whole universe. Its

advantages include that it is colorless, odorless and non-toxic as well as that it is a lightweight gas (Mazloomi & Gomes, 2012). One aspect that makes hydrogen a good alternative for other fuels is its energy content. Hydrogen's energy content is 120 MJ/kg and when compared with gasoline, which has energy content of 44 MJ/kg, it's seen that hydrogen's energy content is almost three times higher than gasoline's. (U.S. Department of Energy, n.d.)

Even when hydrogen is the most abundant element it does not exist in the molecular form in nature hence there are processes that break the hydrogen molecule from other sources. The three methods to produce hydrogen are steam methane reforming (SMR), electrolysis and gasification. In SMR hydrogen is split from methane, in electrolysis the hydrogen is split from water and in gasification coal or biomass can be used for example (Xing et al., 2021). As hydrogen can be classified as a sustainable fuel it is only truly 100% emission free if it is produced with water electrolyzer with renewable energy. Today the problem lies in the fact that less than 5 % of hydrogen is produced this way. (Xing et al., 2021)

Hydrogen is an appealing fuel since it produces minimal emissions if any. For example, with fuel cell applications only water and heat are the by-products (Baldi et al., 2022, 61). This is presented in Equation 2.

Gas turbine running on 100 % hydrogen eliminates the CO₂ emissions. Nevertheless, it will still produce some NO_x emissions because of the composition of compressed air. The emissions, however, are below standard values. (Amirouche et al., 2024)

Hydrogen has various advantages but also a few challenges as fuel. Even though hydrogen has a high energy density per kilogram, its density per cubic meter is very small in gaseous form. The comparison of different maritime fuels' volumetric energy density is presented in Figure 14. Hydrogen requires a lot of storage space, and the storage compartment must be able to handle the high pressure needed for storing hydrogen (Mazloomi & Gomes, 2012). The corrosive nature of hydrogen can cause hydrogen embrittlement to the steel materials in the delivery and storage systems. In hydrogen embrittlement hydrogen dissolves into steel causing stress concentration that is greater than the strength limit of the steel which causes small cracks to the steel structure. Hydrogen leaks easily from even a small crack because it has high diffusivity, small molecular weight and low viscosity. There is no cure to hydrogen

embrittlement, but the affecting factors are known. They include hydrogen concentration, ambient pressure and temperature, exposure time, stress state, mechanical properties, microstructure, surface conditions and the nature of the material crack front. (Yang et al., 2023)

Figure 14. Volumetric energy densities of different marine fuels (Placek, 2023)

Figure 14 gives each of the marine fuels their volumetric energy density. Hydrogen doesn't perform well on the list. However, as stated before when hydrogen and gasoline are compared in mass energy density, hydrogen takes the win with the mass energy density of around 120 MJ/kg with lower heating value (LHV) (Engineering ToolBox, n.d.). Figure 15 shows the mass energy density of most of the marine fuels in Figure 16 with higher heating value (HHV).

Figure 15. Mass energy density of different marine fuels (Engineering ToolBox, n.d.)

HHV is used since the reference didn't have the value of LHV for ammonia. The results differ from Figure 14 drastically. Hydrogen takes the first place, and the energy density is almost three times higher than with methane that takes the second place. Even with LHV hydrogen has the highest energy density out of the marine fuels listed. (Engineering ToolBox, n.d.)

Table 1. presents the values for molecular hydrogen, H_2 . The reason behind using molecular hydrogen as a fuel and not atomic hydrogen comes from the chemical properties of these two. Atomic hydrogen or H is much more unstable and very reactive making storage, transportation and usage impossible. H_2 on the other hand, is the opposite and makes a great energy carrier and fuel for different energy systems. Table 1 includes molecular hydrogens properties.

Table 1. Properties of hydrogen (Zhang et al., 2023)

Parameters	Value
LHV [MJ/kg]	-118.8
HHV [MJ/kg]	143
Boiling temperature at 1 atm [°C]	-253
Melting temperature [°C]	-259
Critical temperature [°C]	-240.01
Critical pressure [MPa]	1.3
Density (gaseous form) [kg/m ³]	0.08987
Density (liquid form) [kg/m ³]	70.85
Heat capacity (gaseous form) [kJ/kgK]	14.3
Heat capacity (liquid form) [kJ/kgK]	8.1

As storing hydrogen is one of the main challenges for marine integration, different storage solutions need to be considered. The alternative fuel storage solutions for pure hydrogen are using a hydrogen carrier such as ammonia (NH₃) and Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHC), hydrogen produced from methane reforming or using methanol in High Temperature PEM fuel cells (HTPEMFC). (Baldi et al., 2022, 62)

Hydrogens usage as a fuel in gas turbine cannot be brought to use on a bigger scale just yet since on top of the other challenges, there is a paucity of the ports where refueling can happen. (Baldi et al., 2022, 61)

3.3.1. Ammonia

Ammonia is a good option for fueling the maritime industry and a great fuel for gas turbine application since no major improvements or design changes need to be made. It is produced combining nitrogen and hydrogen in conditions with high pressure and temperature with the help of catalyst. Being compounded of nitrogen and hydrogen means, it doesn't have molecular carbon thus doesn't produce CO₂ emissions when combusted. To have zero carbon emissions, the used ammonia in marine vessels requires the ammonia to be categorized as

green. This means only renewable energy sources such as wind and solar power are acceptable for production. (Thurman, a, 2023)

Ammonia has potential to reduce GHG emissions, but it challenges the marine engines with its corrosive nature and this property makes additional maintenance mandatory. Hydrogen and gaseous ammonia share the same problem: storage issues. Ammonia needs a large storage capacity since its volumetric efficiency and energy density are much lower compared to fossil fuels in use. Vessels' operating range is heavily impacted by the dimensions of the storage unit for ammonia. Ammonia is also toxic, and which makes handling it difficult thus when designing ammonia fuel systems, safety should be in mind. (Thurman, a, 2023)

Another challenge with ammonia is its production since it is not sustainable yet (Thurman, 2023). It is possible to use renewable energy to produce green ammonia and generate nearly zero GHGs on a WtW basis. Generality of ammonia used as a fuel is categorized as grey meaning it's produced with conventional energy sources. Using grey ammonia is less profitable for the environment since its production generates more GHGs than using conventional marine fuels themselves. (European Maritime Safety Agency, 2022)

Because of the chemical compound of ammonia, NO_x emissions will appear when burnt. Equation 5 presents the chemical reaction when ammonia reacts with oxygen.

The potential of nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions brings uncertainty to the usage of ammonia since handling it is one of the biggest unknowns. Developing catalysts for N_2O emissions is one way to ensure the sustainability of ammonia. (Thurman, a, 2023)

To this day there is not much ammonia available for the shipping industry as it is competing with fertilizer and energy industries. Starting up production takes time as building an ammonia plant takes up to six years. On a global scale over 200 low-carbon ammonia facilities are being planned. As the marine industry starts to adopt ammonia as a fuel on a bigger scale, the fuel bunkering network needs to grow with it. The bunkering system can be fixed or mobile. Mobile bunkering systems refer to transportable tanks whereas fixed systems are located at ports or fueling stations. With fixed bunkering the infrastructure needs to be developed to be able to handle both liquid and gaseous ammonia. (Thurman, a, 2023)

3.3.2. Renewable methane and natural gas

Liquified and compressed natural gases are good options when going towards cleaner fuels since they decrease emissions by 5-21% compared to using HFO. LNG is a drop-in fuel so it can be used on already existing systems and no extra investments are needed (Wärtsilä, b, 2025). Natural gas gains its liquid form in atmospheric pressure and at the temperature of -162 °C. It can be stored in insulated tanks. Natural gas can be called compressed natural gas when it is stored in atmospheric temperature and in high pressure, between 300 to 700 bars. Out of the two LNG is more favorable to use in marine propulsion because it has higher energy density than CNG. (Baldi et al., 2022, 59)

Natural gas is typically 85-95 % methane. The chemical and combustion properties of the fuel allow SO_x emissions to be removed almost completely. The NO_x emissions can expect a drop of 85% because of the lean burn combustion process in spark ignited and dual fuel engines. Hence there is no need for emission reduction systems that are needed with oil fuels (Baldi et al., 2022, 59). Natural gas can have its flaws since it's made with methane. Methane leakage or slip can occur when burning the fuel. If methane gets into the atmosphere, it affects greatly the GHG footprint of the fuel. (Wärtsilä b, 2025)

LNG can be used as its own or natural gas and hydrogen can be blended and used as mix. When the ships are at the ports it is more strategic to use a hydrogen mix to obey the emission limits. Transitioning to sustainable shipping LNG is a good choice since it has fairly low WtW GHG emission factor, 76 g/MJ. (Barsi et al. 2024)

Renewable methane is also termed as renewable natural gas (RNG) or synthetic natural gas (SNG). Methane would serve the same purpose as natural gas but would be a renewable choice. Chemical composition of natural gas and methane are comparable, and this is why methane can be transported with the same pipelines as natural gas. Because of this there are no concerns about blending limits and reduction in natural gas use. Renewable methane is produced by combining renewable energy powered electrolysis and air-captured CO₂ or by removing impurities from biogas that has been produced from waste or landfill gas. Biogas based methane can be also called biomethane. Producing methane from organic waste by anaerobic digestion is a recommended method by the Intergovernmental Panel and Climate Change (IPCC) since it helps to reduce emissions in waste management sector. Methane is very abundant since it takes between 54 and 73 % of biogas' composition. Methane can be

produced with hydrogen and captured carbon dioxide. This methane can only be called renewable if hydrogen is classified as green. (Cha et al., 2024)

When methane is burnt and reacts with oxygen, carbon dioxide and water are the byproducts.

Including a direct air capture of carbon monoxide, while using renewable methane as a fuel, helps with achieving carbon negative emissions. (Choe et al., 2023)

In 2022 the EU released their REPowerEU Plan to phase out Europe's independency on Russian fossil fuels. In the Plan it was outlined that there is a clear need for scale up in biomethane production by 2030. Production needs to reach a capacity of 35 billion cubic meters per year by 2030. The EU also wants to promote the usage of municipal waste rather than food and feedstock for better land use, just like IPPC. (European Commission d, n.d.)

3.3.3. Methanol

Methanol is highly toxic, flammable and colorless biodegradable wood alcohol. As a fuel it still produces emissions but far less than diesel combustion. Switching to methanol from diesel would decrease CO₂ emissions by 7 %, SO_x emissions by 99 % and NO_x emissions by 60 %. These numbers are only reachable if green methanol, which is made from biomass or captured CO₂ and green hydrogen, is utilized. (Thurman, b, 2023)

Equations 6 & 7 show the chemical reaction when methanol is made with hydrogen and when methanol is burned and reacts with oxygen.

When methanol is produced with hydrogen:

When methanol reacts with oxygen when burned:

Using grey or brown methanol, that are made with natural gas and coal, will only have a worse impact on the CO₂ emissions than using diesel. Methanol molecules stay the same

despite the production method thus making transition towards green methanol easier over time. (Thurman, b, 2023)

Methanol is biodegradable and miscible with water. Unlike gasoline it doesn't accumulate in water air or soil, making it less of a risk to environment (Candelaresi & Spazzafumo, 2021). Methanol would be very accessible fuel since major ports have storage and handling facilities nearby. Globally over 100 ports have methanol available for fueling. (Thurman, b, 2023)

In the study of Cui et al. (2025) methanol and methane were compared as a fuel for gas turbines and the properties were evaluated from a combustor design point of view. As a result, methanol has greater flexibility for the design of the gas turbine and the performance of methanol combustor surpasses methane combustor. The design for methane can be adapted to methanol combustion without structural modification.

Production of green methanol is low. Only 0,2 % of the total methanol production is green and is mainly produced with biomass gasification. It has been proposed to produce methanol from municipal waste. The increasing need for sustainable fuels makes producing methanol in an environmentally friendly way more interesting. (Sollai et al., 2022)

4. The state of hydrogen fueled gas turbines

This chapter takes a closer look at previous studies regarding hydrogen fueled gas turbine. Hydrogen fueled gas turbine combined cycle is the energy system of this MARPOWER-project. Analyzing the results from previous studies helps to understand better the functions that the cycle should have and gives a look at the state that the industry is at the moment and also what more needs to be done.

4.1. Commercial hydrogen gas turbine systems

Multiple companies have developed a large scale of hydrogen fueled gas turbines, most of them still being used for land applications. Zhou et al. (2024) had compared some of existing hydrogen fueled gas turbines and compared them. In Table 2. are the gas turbines from the article.

Table 2. Hydrogen gas turbines in the market (Zhou et al., 2024)

Name	Hydrogen vol %
General Electric	DLN 2.6e combustor:50%
Mitsubishi Power	The multi-nozzle combustor: 30%
	The multi-cluster combustor: 80%
	Diffusion combustors: 100%
Siemens	Siemens aeroderivatives: 100%
	Siemens industrial gas turbines: 60%
	Small industrial turbine: 20%
Ansaldo Energia	Original Equipment: GT36H: 0–50%
THM gas turbines	60%

Mitsubishi launched in 2023 a gas turbine that runs on 30% hydrogen and 70 % natural gas. The demonstration was remarkable since it was the first power generation test on a large-scale gas turbine while using 30 % hydrogen and being connected to the power grid, using hydrogen that was produced and stored on the same site. In 2024 the goal was to continue

upgrading the hydrogen percentage to 50 % and all the way up to 100 %. (Mitsubishi, 2023). Today it is possible to run the gas turbine with 60 % hydrogen with Dry Low NO_x combustor. Mitsubishi has been working on H-25 gas turbine and Multi-Cluster Combustor. With a diffusion type of combustor, the H-25 can run on 100 % hydrogen and is capable of providing exhaust gas temperatures up to 569 °C. The Multi-Cluster Combustor is still in development state but should run on 100 % hydrogen in the near future. (Mitsubishi, n.d.)

Siemens has gas turbines for marine application, but they run on conventional fuels. When compared to natural gas, Siemens has gas turbines that enable the CO₂ reduction to 100 %. Siemens has 17 gas turbines that work with hydrogen, only SGT-A35 can work with 100 % hydrogen. This model has a good reputation on offshore application but like most models it also runs on fossil fuels. (Siemens, n.d.)

As ICE is the leading engine type for marine vessels there is room for studies about marine gas turbines. General Electric (GE) has been producing gas turbines for multiple decades, even ones working with hydrogen. GE has GE LM2500 Family of gas turbines that includes LM2500XPRESS gas turbine. This family of gas turbines is used in marine applications and has up to 75 % hydrogen capability as a fuel. GE has been working for a long time providing marine gas turbines for multiple countries. The LM2500 aeroderivative gas turbine is compatible for marine endeavors of all sizes. It can be used for simple cycle and combined cycle (GE Vernova, 2025). Table 3. presents parameters for LM2500XPRESS gas turbine from both simple cycle and 1 x 1 combined cycle meaning there is 1 gas turbine and 1 steam turbine in the HRSG. The model has a hydrogen capability of 35%. (GE Vernova, 2025)

Table 3. Comparison of LM2500XPRESS+ DLE (15ppm NO_x) (GE Vernova, 2025)

	Simple Cycle	Combined Cycle 1 x 1
Net output (MW)	30.6	44.5
Net heat rate (kJ/kWh, LHV)	9811	6674
Net efficiency (% , LHV)	36.7	53.3

This gas turbine model reaches NO_x levels as low as 15 ppm (parts per million) and has Dry-Low Emission (DLE) technology. DLE technology enables the lean-burn operation, and this helps with emission reductions. (Faqih et al., 2022)

GE has also designed gas turbines for Queen Mary II owned by Cunard Line. The power is produced with a combined diesel and gas turbine (CODAG) propulsion system. This means the gas turbine works on conventional fuels, not on hydrogen. (Ammar & Alshammari, 2018)

In 2022 Goldmeer and Catillaz published a paper about GE Verona's experience, requirements and implications for the use of hydrogen in gas turbines. Figure 16 shows their pathway to how much it is possible to mitigate carbon emissions with each cycle and fuel.

Figure 16. GE Verona estimation for emission reduction (Goldmeer & Catillaz, 2022)

It is unsure what gas is meant by the gas that produces emission reduction of 45 % compared to using coal. The paper mentions natural gas so that could assumably be it. HA refers to high-efficiency, air-cooled. As stated before, GE Vernova has achieved a gas turbine working with hydrogen being 75 %.

4.2. Recent studies of marine gas turbines

Based on the research found, hydrogen fueled gas turbines for marine use hasn't been studied much. Hydrogen finding its place as the primary fuel is still an ongoing process as the infrastructure isn't there yet. Barsi et al. (2024) had published a paper in 2024 about

designing a small-scale marine gas turbine. In the paper they suggested that for auxiliary power generator both micro and small gas turbines could be a great choice. Their gas turbine combined cycle includes centrifugal compressor and radial turbine. The bottoming cycle includes HRSG and steam turbine. The input data included TIT of 950°C and LNG was supposedly used as a fuel. The compressor pressure ratio was 6.5 and the turbine pressure ratio was 6.0. Their conclusions were that 5 MW small-scale gas turbine is feasible to assemble for marine propulsion. This is positive news since the gas turbine in this MARPOWER project is in the same range. With combustor and turbine optimization the overall cycle efficiency ended up being 41%. The goal for the future is to use e-LNG as fuel to comply with the emission regulations. The main challenges included the achievement of competitive performance that would be comparable to axial GT and marine diesel engines of the same size.

Alkhaledi et al. (2022) did a techno-environmental assessment of Flettner rotors as assistance propulsion for a gas turbine on a tanker ship that was fueled 100% with liquid hydrogen. Flettner rotor is a vertical cylinder that rotates around its axis. The blowing wind creates a pressure difference on the rotor that is due the opposite signs of the wind's velocity. The velocity difference is induced by the rotation of the rotor. The pressure difference generates a lift force perpendicular to the wind's direction. The lift and drag forces combined result in a thrust driving the ship (Baldi et al., 2022, 65). With this 100% renewable propulsion system the energy sector would reach the high-efficiency and low-emission targets. The tanker ship is 370 meters long and 75 meters wide. The displacement tonnage is 230,000 tons of liquified hydrogen which indicates the weight of a full tank. The gas turbine in the ship has a pressure ratio of 23.1, exhaust gas temperature of 840,3 K, fuel flow of 0.7485 kg/s and the power output is 36.2 MW with 40.3% thermal efficiency. On the steam side the superheated steam temperature is 559.8°C at 60 bar. The pinch point temperature difference (PPTD) is set to be 7.5°C and steam power output is 14.35 MW. The ship was evaluated in three seasons and with two voyages. As a result, the maximum efficiency with only COGAS was 55.5% on the voyage between Marseille and Algeria and 55% on the voyage between Tangier and Southampton. The Flettner rotos enhanced the efficiency with 1% in both cases. (Alkhaledi, 2022)

Some papers are focused on reviewing hydrogen's chances as a maritime sector fuel. Nader R. Ammar has published a paper with Alshammari (Ammar & Alshamma, 2018) and with

Gohary (Gohary & Ammar, 2016). In both the hydrogen was discussed as a fuel for gas turbines and in both papers, they come to the conclusion that the properties of hydrogen vary from other fuels greatly. Adaptation of hydrogen to waterborne vehicles is still challenging and modifications are need for optimum performance. In Gohary and Ammar's paper (2016) they did a thermodynamical analysis of alternative fuels for marine gas turbine power plants. The gas turbine that was used in the study was the LM2500 gas turbine. The power of the gas turbine was 25 MW and the efficiency was 37 %. Pressure ratio was 18:1.

In 2016 Gohary and Seddiek wrote a paper about utilization of alternative maritime fuels for gas turbines on board. In the study they compared hydrogen and natural gas with diesel to determine how well diesel could be replaced. They then came to the conclusion that hydrogen alongside with natural gas can replace the diesel fuels in the industry. It was specified that natural gas would be the solution that could be implemented in a shorter time range as hydrogen requires significant modifications to reach an optimum performance. The study resulted in gas turbine thermal efficiency being 1% less with hydrogen when compared to using diesel and the fuel consumption was over 63% less with hydrogen.

5. The MARPOWER project

This chapter focuses on the goals of the MARPOWER project, and the hydrogen fueled combined cycle gas turbine process that is the main target in this thesis. As hydrogen is chosen to be the fuel in this case, it is mandatory to recognize the advantages and challenges that come with it. The properties of hydrogen need to be taken into account when the gas turbine is designed. The EU and IMO have set ambitious goals for reducing the carbon intensity of the marine sector. The MARPOWER project contributes to these goals and focuses on decarbonizing the maritime sector globally by developing a highly efficient two-shaft gas turbine-based energy conversion system that utilizes sustainable fuels instead of fossil fuels. These alternatives fuels include green methane, green methanol, hydrogen and ammonia. At the end, this project aims to mitigate GHG emissions and marine pollution, and this way protect the oceans and coastal ecosystems. The focus points of the project lie on energy efficiency and implementing the alternative, low-carbon fuels to gas turbines with minimal modification to existing combustion systems (MARPOWER, 2025). The electrical efficiency target is between 50 and 55% and the overall electrical and thermal efficiency target is 73-76%. Fuel-flexible combustion of the system ensures that the combustor is able to run on 100% hydrogen or on one of the other zero-emission fuels. (European Commission, 2024)

Key features of the gas turbine include scalability, safety and resilience to fuel variability. As the goals are set on a global scale the system should be suitable for short and long-distance marine vessels. This ensures economic competitiveness over fossil fuel systems. (MARPOWER, 2025)

5.1. Hydrogen fueled combined cycle

In Figure 17 the focused process is presented. The system consists of generators, turbines, compressors, a burning chamber and of two types of heat exchangers: a recuperator and an intercooler. The bottoming cycle WHRS is a single pressure level steam turbine cycle that includes a WHB, a waste heat turbine, a condenser and a feed pump.

Figure 17. Ship's energy system

In Figure 17, first the air enters the low-pressure compressor where it is pre-compressed. After that the compressed air enters the air-to-liquid intercooler where the air is cooled down with seawater. Next the air enters a set of high-pressure compressors, where it is compressed more. After a high-pressure compressors, the air flows to the recuperator. Recuperator is a heat exchanger where the air absorbs the heat from the exhaust gas that flows on the other side and then enters the burning chamber. Recuperator's purpose on the process is to increase the efficiency.

Hydrogen is injected to the burning chamber where it reacts with the compressed air. The result is hot water vapor and that enters the high-pressure turbine that has cooled blades. After high-pressure turbine, the water vapor enters a low-pressure turbine. There the vapor goes to the recuperator to cool down as it releases the heat to the compressed air. To maximize the energy usage, the exhaust gas enters a waste heat boiler where it is used to steam up the water into a superheated steam. The superheated steam goes through the waste heat turbine to power a generator. The vapor after the turbine goes through a condenser and the condensed water is pumped back to the boiler with a feed water pump. After the exhaust

gas has gone through the boiler, it is released into the air. The exhaust gas mostly consists of water vapor but has some NO_x emissions too.

After different cases were examined, some adjustments were made. In the previous version there was an intercooler between the two high pressure compressors. This was later left out because of spacing issues on the shaft. The positive gains from the intercooler were not significant so it was better to leave it out. Even though the gas turbine efficiency dropped slightly the complete efficiency of gas turbine and waste heat recovery system increased.

Turbine inlet temperature for the vapor was set for one case to be above $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and for another case it is above $1300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This affects the cooling need of the turbine blades. The cooling vapor is taken from the air after the intercooler. As can be seen from Figure 18, after the cooled air has left the turbine, it is combined with the exhaust gas that leaves the low-pressure turbine.

The pressure ratio of gas turbine cycle is 12:1. If referred to the study done by Goswami and Kreith (2019) then the pressure ratio of the gas turbine lies in a very optimum value for high efficiency. Gas turbines can have a pressure ratio as high as 40:1 (Boyce, 2012). Based on that, the pressure ratio of 12:1 in this MARPOWER gas turbine is on the lower side of the pressure ratio range. As recuperators are not used on high pressure ratios, it is applicable to have one in this cycle to increase efficiency. (Sayma, 2017)

5.1.1. Gas turbine: how hydrogen effects the design

To understand the importance of proper gas turbine design and especially the combustor design, natural gas can be used as a reference fuel to give some perspective. With natural gas, in gas combustors the fuel is injected to the airflow at an angle and from a specified distance upstream of the flame. If the length of the premixing region for NG combustion is very small, even zero, it results in non-premixed flame and the reaction rate peaks at the stoichiometry. When compared to a more optimal region length, air and NG can form a homogenous mixture before entering the burning chamber. This results in a lean combustion that is the goal. With natural gas the flame stabilization is secured because of the large recirculation zone achieved by highly swirling air. Success is achieved because the flame

doesn't come in contact with the fuel injection point which is ensured with the airflow velocity. (Tingas, 2023, 409-410)

Natural gas and hydrogen have very different compositions. If in a gas turbine that works with NG only the fuel is changed to hydrogen and all the other components stay the same, problems will occur. Hydrogen has higher flame speed than natural gas. There is a higher risk that the flame flashes back near the fuel injection point. In flashback the flame speed overtakes the flow velocity. This causes material and safety problems on feeding nozzles. (Cecere et al., 2023). For this reason, it is why either very small injection holes or very high velocity is needed for hydrogen when it is injected, or special care is required to avoid boundary layers and separation. Also splitting the air to flow into many parallel ducts would also be a possible solution. Here hydrogen could be injected in a crossflow to the air flow or parallel configuration. This would help the flame to detach from the injection point because the air and hydrogen both have high velocities. More research needs to be done on the stabilization mechanism (Tingas, 2023, 410). Figure 18 shows how hydrogen is injected to the gas turbine combustion system and the difference between the two techniques.

Figure 18. Hydrogen injection techniques (Tingas, 2023, 411)

The top picture in Figure 18 shows the situation if hydrogen is injected to the combustor from two spots and cross-flow into the air flow. It shows that the high possibility of a flashback exists, and cooling is needed for the hydrogen feeding nozzles. (Tingas, 2023, 411)

The bottom picture shows the situation when hydrogen is injected from many small holes and in a co-flow with air flow. Using small injection holes is a state-of-the-art technology, and multiple variants are under development. Here the idea is to stabilize the flame with burner inlet plate. (Tingas, 2023, 411)

As mentioned in Figure 19, here the important factor is low NO_x emissions. To achieve that, the significant mixing of air and hydrogen must be accomplished before flame. The relation

of the location of injection holes and air flow into the combustion chamber influences the distribution of the mixture. This can have an important effect not only on the shape and location of the flame but also to the NO_x emissions (Tingas, 2023, 410). Another characteristic that needs to be noted when working with hydrogen is adiabatic flame temperature. Adiabatic flame temperature refers to the maximum temperature of the heat that is released from the combustion process and that heats up the combustion products. Hydrogen has a quite high adiabatic flame temperature, between 2318 K and 2400 K when other fuels such as methane and propane have an adiabatic flame temperature staying under 2300 K. High adiabatic temperature can also lead to an increased level of NO_x emissions. (Cecere et al., 2023)

As stated, hydrogen is a much more reactive fuel than for example natural gas. The difference of the flame speed of these two can be seen from Figure 19. When hydrogen is mixed with other fuels the reactivity of the mix increases as well (Cecere et al., 2023). So when changing the composition of the fuel whether it is purely hydrogen or a mix of hydrogen and another fuel the combustion chamber characteristics must be re-evaluated in every case.

Figure 19. Laminar flame speed versus equivalence ratio (Dong et al., 2010)

Figure 19 presents the laminar flame speeds of H_2 /air mixture and NG/air mixture. These two fuel mixes have their peak at very different spots. The maximum flame speed for H_2 is 2.933 m/s and for NG it is 0.374 m/s. H_2 has the maximum value when equivalence ratio is 1.7 and NG has it when equivalence ratio in 1.1. The data is based on the article from Dong

et al. (2010). As no actual data was available this figure has been made based on their figures. The conditions in the measurement are 293 K and 1 atm and the burner diameter is 2 mm. The high flame speed of hydrogen causes problems with material resistance and safety, increasing the critical strain rate and minimizing the quenching possibilities of the flame. (Cecere et al., 2023)

Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR) is doing research on the combustion of hydrogen in the MARPOWER project. Cecere (2023) wrote in their paper that with gas turbines there are challenges during testing and operation with thermoacoustic instability. The problem comes from the unsteady phase heat release which leads to large amplitude pressure oscillations (Cecere et al., 2023). In 2024 DLR published an article about successful usage of 100% hydrogen in a micro gas turbine. They have created a new burner and an adapted control system to make it possible to fuel the gas turbine with either 100% hydrogen or mixture of hydrogen and natural gas. The important step on the design was to make sure that the flame would not flash back into the burner nozzles and cause damage to them. DLR's newest concept on gas turbine design is a jet-stabilised burner that is optimized for hydrogen usage. Success is achieved with air and fuel nozzles that are arranged to ring formation. The ring formation creates a backflow in the burning chamber which makes it possible for the exhaust gases to move back to the nozzles and be mixed with fresh fuel mixture. This doesn't only stabilize the flame but also lowers the temperature in the burning chamber. (DLR, 2024)

5.1.2. Fuel's influence on waste heat recovery system

In WHRS, pinch point temperature difference plays a vital role in design parameter optimization, but it can also have limiting factors. Acid dew point (ADP) is one limiting factor that sets the range for the PPTD. ADP is the temperature at which the acid vapor in the flue gas begins to condense (Zuo, 2020). Normally acid vapor is referred to as sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4). As presented in the equations in chapter 3.3, none of the alternative fuels include sulfur thus they won't produce any emissions containing it. The problem lies more on the conventional fuels in the marine sector as they do include sulfur. Sulphur acid is formed when sulfur trioxide (SO_3) reacts with water vapor. Both components are in gaseous form.

Sulfur acid is corrosive acid. This is why the PPTD in the boiler needs to be carefully determined if fuel contains sulfur. Water isn't corrosive and since in the boiler the other side is dedicated to handling water in liquid and vapor phase, the pipes should handle the water vapor of the exhaust gas as well. The properties of exhaust gas from hydrogen burning don't set boundaries to PPTD.

6. Design parameter calculation methods

This chapter includes the methodology part of the thesis. Here the calculations and chosen methods for the MARPOWER project process are presented. The chapter focuses on how the cycle parameters can be optimized and how they affect the design. The literature for validating the results is also presented in this chapter.

6.1. Seawater temperature

The effect of seawater temperature needs to be studied to see its effects on the process parameters. Boundary conditions need to be stated for the cycle since not all parameters can be optimized. Seawater is used in the intercooler to cool down the air from low-pressure compressor. The wanted outlet temperature for the air side in the intercooler is 25°C. To achieve this set value, the water inlet temperature needs to be obtained to set boundaries for the process. The depth where the water used in air-to-liquid intercooler is taken from is assumed to be close to the surface. The water directly from the surface is not used to avoid surface contamination and to ensure a stable water supply to the intercooler.

As a methodology used to determine a seawater temperature for this case, an article from Finnish Meteorological Institute (2023) is used. The article has used data from the Sea of Bothnia which will work as the reference point for the rest of the calculations. Data from both winter and summer time is collected so the intercooler graphs of both seasons can be compared.

The smallest temperature difference in the heat exchanger is called the approach temperature. It is also a design parameter for the intercooler and in this case, it is calculated as in Equation 16.

$$T_{approach} = T_{a,out} - T_{w,in max} \quad (16)$$

, where $T_{w,in max}$ is the maximum inlet temperature for seawater, $T_{a,out}$ is the set air outlet temperature and $T_{approach}$ is the temperature difference between the first two temperatures, also called as the approach temperature.

Mathur (2024) stated in his paper that with liquid-to-liquid heat exchanger, the temperature approach can be as low as 1.1°C. The parameters that are critical for setting the possible approach temperature are mass flow of the cooling liquid and the size of the heat transfer areas and this is linked to the size of the intercooler itself.

6.2. Waste heat recovery boiler

Waste heat recovery boiler is added to increase the energy efficiency of the process and to also improve the fuel savings. Boiler calculation originally had 2 pressure levels, high- and low-pressure one. It was decided to continue with a single pressure boiler.

The stages in the boiler are shown in Figure 20. If evaluated from the water/steam side, the stages start with economizer, next is evaporator and at the end the superheater. The pinch point temperature difference is the smallest temperature difference between the source and the working fluid. It is located between economizer and evaporator.

Figure 20. Heat rate in the WHRB

One parameter that needs to be optimized is the exhaust gas boiler outlet temperature. As this exhaust gas is released into the air it would be better to use the heat from it to heat the water in the boiler rather than waste it. The exhaust gas outlet temperature is strongly linked to the pinch point temperature difference. Increasing the exhaust gas boiler outlet temperature increases PPTD. If the PPTD is too small, it means that the heat exchanger surfaces have to be large for enough heat to convey from the working fluid to the water. As ships offer only very limited space for the energy system the devices need to be as compact as possible. Based on the literature available, the optimal PPTD for the waste heat recovery

boiler is usually between 5 to 20 °C. This range ensures an efficient heat recovery and economic feasibility. Wu et al. (2014) stated in their paper that in some studies, the range is between 8 to 20 K and in some studies, it is between 3 to 7 K. Their own results show that the optimal PPTD range from the perspective of exergy recovery was 5-12 K

6.2.1. Pinch point temperature difference

The pinch point is the point in the WHRS system where the temperature difference is the smallest between the working fluid and the source. Determining the optimal pinch point temperature difference or PPTD is important since it affects the heat transfer areas on the steam side. Achieving an optimal PPTD is also important from an economic point of view.

The exhaust gas outlet temperature or the stack temperature in the boiler has a huge impact on PPTD. If the stack temperature is too high this means less heat transfer in the boiler itself. As the outlet exhaust gas isn't used for energy production after the boiler, it is released into the air. The goal is to have a lower stack temperature since it reflects to the efficiency of the boiler positively and results in higher fuel-to-steam efficiency. (Bhatia, n.d.)

In this case Newton's method is used to find the PPTD. Newton's method is used for solving equations, but it can be tailored for optimization purposes. As an optimization method Newton's method is simple and linear. With this method the Excel calculates automatically the boiler outlet temperature for the exhaust gas based on the pinch point temperature that is given to it. Newton's method is implemented into a macro and a button was created to run the macro when the pinch point temperature was changed (Polyak, 2011). Newton's method for calculating the next value in the iteration process is shown in Equation 8.

$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{f(x)}{f'(x)} \quad (8)$$

For the derivative function, the numerical derivative is used. The simple approximation of the first derivative is shown in Equation 9.

$$f'(x) = \frac{f(x+k) - f(x)}{k} \quad (9)$$

where $k > 0$ and is determined step to help to solve the calculation. The goal is to find a value that leads the function $f(x)$ in Equation 8 to be zero. Equation 10. shows the function used in Excel.

$$T_{out,B+1} = T_{out,B} - \frac{(T_{eg} - T_s) - PPTD_{target}}{\frac{\left(\left((T_{eg} - T_s) - PPTD_{target}\right) + k\right) - (T_{eg} - T_s) - PPTD_{target}}{k}} \quad (10)$$

, where T_{eg} is the exhaust gas evaporator outlet temperature, T_s is the steam economizer outlet temperature, $PPTD_{target}$ is the set PPTD value and k is a step used for the iteration. The optimal PPTD range is validated based on literature available since the boiler manufacturers have their own specs for more specific PPTD value.

6.2.1. Steam side heat transfer areas

For the steam side of the WHRB the water coming from the feed water tank is around 50 °C and the pressure is around 6 bar. Based on this and the pressure loss in the boiler, the steps in the cycle can be calculated. For full calculation, the hot end temperature difference in the boiler needs to be determined. Based on this the superheated steam outlet temperature can be calculated as well how much heat the exhaust gas conveys to the steam.

The pressure for the superheated steam is known based on the pressure losses in the evaporator. When the temperature is set, the enthalpy can be determined from the log (p)-h diagram for water. The vapor is superheated on the right side of the figure in the graph.

The heat transfer areas for economizer, evaporator and superheater need to be determined to see how they correlate with the PPTD. Equation 14 is used for all three areas.

$$A = \frac{Q}{U \cdot T_{LMTD} \cdot F} \quad (14)$$

, where Q is the heat rate, U is the overall heat transfer coefficient, T_{LMTD} is the log mean temperature difference, and F is the LMTD correction factor.

6.2.2. Exhaust gas thermal power

The exhaust gas thermal power indicates how much energy is transferred from the exhaust gas to the steam. The boiler has some losses so with the thermal power and the losses the heat rate to steam can be calculated. Exhaust gas thermal power is calculated as in Equation 12.

$$P = q_m \cdot (h_{eg,in} - h_{eg,out}) \quad (12)$$

, where q_m is the mass flow of the exhaust gas, $h_{eg,in}$ is the enthalpy of the exhaust gas entering the boiler and $h_{eg,out}$ is the enthalpy of the exhaust gas exiting the boiler

The boiler efficiency is 98%. Based on this and the exhaust gas thermal power, the heat rate to steam can be calculated

$$Q = P \cdot \eta_B \quad (13)$$

, where η_B is the boiler efficiency and P exhaust thermal power.

6.3. Net electric efficiency of the cycle

There is no internal electricity consumption, so all the electrical energy produced goes to powering the propulsion system. The net electric efficiency is calculated for the gas turbine cycle and for the combined gas turbine cycle to see how much the WHRS affects the efficiency. Net electric efficiency is calculated as in Equation 15.

$$\eta_{el,net} = \frac{P_{net}}{P_{fuel}} \cdot 100 \quad (15)$$

, where P_{net} is the net electric power output and P_{fuel} is the fuel power. The efficiency for electric power output is 97%.

The results need to be compared with the PPTD as well to see how they correlate with each other. The other factor affecting the efficiency is the seawater temperature. The effect is studied with Excel calculations to determine the connection between the cooling fluid and net electric efficiency of the combined cycle.

7. Results

In this chapter the results for parameter calculation are presented and compared. The results for gas turbine side as well as the WHRS are shown but the focus points are on comparing the two different cases and on seeing how PPTD and seawater temperature change affects other parameters. As multiple parameters are linked, some boundaries need to be set. First, the seawater temperature's role in the system is evaluated as well as the temperatures effect on the intercooler. As the PPTD also has its effect on the net electric efficiency and the seawater temperature changes during the year, after comparing the temperature between summer and winter, the other parameters' effect on the efficiency is analyzed with the winter seawater temperature. Later with PPTD analysis, the graphs use the minimum PPTD value. When analyzing seawater's effect on efficiency, the minimum PPTD value is also used. As this thesis is part of an EU-funded project that is still ongoing, the results are rounded up thus they aren't exactly the values from the real calculations.

Table 4 has the starting values for the process calculation gathered. Table 5 has all the important efficiencies listed. Two tables were created to improve the reading of the values.

Table 4. Process calculation values

Parameter	Value
Intake air temperature [°C]	15
Intake air pressure [bar]	1
Intake air mass flow, case 1 [kg/s]	12.7
Intake air mass flow, case 2 [kg/s]	11.7
Pressure ratio	12:1
Intercooler cold end temperature difference [°C]	15
Hydrogen combustor inlet temperature [°C]	30
Hydrogen mass flow rate [kg/s]	0.09
Intercooler water side mass flow [kg/s]	10
Exhaust gas boiler inlet temperature, case 1 [°C]	265
Exhaust gas boiler inlet pressure, case 1 [bar]	1
Exhaust gas boiler inlet temperature, case 2 [°C]	290
Exhaust gas boiler inlet pressure, case 2 [bar]	1
Economizer inlet temperature [°C]	50
Economizer inlet pressure [bar]	6

In Table 5 LP stands for low pressure and HP stands for high pressure. There are two high-pressure compressors back-to-back in the system, so number 1 indicates the compressor after the low-pressure compressor and number 2 indicates the compressor after the first compressor.

Table 5. System efficiencies

Parameter	Efficiency, η
LP and HP1 compressor efficiency [%]	86
HP2 compressor efficiency [%]	85
HP turbine isentropic efficiency [%]	87
LP turbine isentropic efficiency [%]	91
Gas turbine mechanical efficiency [%]	97
Generator electrical efficiency [%]	97
Electrical power output to grid efficiency [%]	97
Boiler efficiency [%]	98

7.1. Seawater temperature

The seawater temperature varies greatly in the world, being the hottest on the Equator region. This temperature of the seawater affects the net electric efficiency of the combined process cycle. It is assumed that the seawater onboard is pumped from couple meters below the sea level. As a reference point, the data collected by the Finnish Meteorological Institute (2023) that compares the temperature from the Sea of Bothnia is used. The data is represented in Figure 21.

Figure 21. Temperature of the Sea of Bothnia (Finnish Meteorological Institute, 2023)

As seen from the data, whether it is summer or winter the seawater temperature doesn't change in the first 15 meters. During the summer the temperature is about 17°C and during winter it is about 1°C. The heat rate of the intercooler is based on the temperature drop that is calculated in the air side. Based on this, the temperature difference on the liquid side is calculated. With this data, two cases can be visualized for the intercooler. Figures 22 and 23 present the intercooler graph where the seawater is used to cool down compressed air.

Figure 22. Intercooler, seawater inlet 1°C

Figure 23. Intercooler, seawater inlet 17°C

As a boundary condition, temperature difference at the cool end is set for 15°C in the intercooler calculation. With water inlet temperature of 1°C the air exits the intercooler at 16°C and with inlet temperature of 17°C the air exits at 32°C. The air enters the intercooler in both case at the same temperature, around 154°C. Because of the set temperature difference at the cold end, the seawater's outlet temperature changes while the inlet temperature changes. The higher the seawater inlet temperature is, the lower the heat rate in the intercooler is. At the same time the heat transfer area of the intercooler decreases. The

graphs of intercooler stay the same despite the turbine inlet temperature since the water and the air entering the process are the same in both cases.

From the cooled air, a side stream is created to help lower the turbine blade temperature- This helps to mitigate the damage that high heat can cause. After the turbine the air enters the exhaust gas stream, and this mixture enters the recuperator. The same formula that was used to calculate the degree of recuperation can be used to verify the efficiency of the intercooler, and it results in about 0.90 as well. For the rest of the results, the seawater temperature of 1°C is used.

7.2. Pinch point temperature difference

The exhaust gas entering the boiler goes through the recuperator first to convey the heat from it to the air entering the combustor. Two different cases were compared with the difference being the turbine inlet temperature. In case 1 the TIT is above 1200 °C and in case 2 TIT is above 1300 °C.

The degree of recuperation doesn't change as the PPTD changes. The degree of recuperation can be calculated as in Equation 1 in chapter 2.3.1 Recuperator technology. The result of the calculation is about 0.90, which is a typical value among recuperators (Xiao et al., 2017). Figures 24 and 25 show the recuperator graphs for both cases.

Figure 24. Recuperator heat rate, case 1

Figure 25. Recuperator heat rate, case 2

Recuperator graphs are influenced by the turbine inlet temperatures. When comparing the two cases, it's seen that lower TIT results in lower exhaust gas value that then enters the waste heat boiler. In case 2 more thermal energy is available. The combination of exhaust gas after low-pressure turbine and the cooling flow of the high-pressure turbine blades set the total exhaust gas temperature under 700°C in both cases. Air entering the recuperator is at the same temperature in both cases. After the recuperator, the exhaust gas enters the waste heat recovery boiler where the PPTD affects how much heat can be recovered from it.

The calculation for PPTD was run in Excel. The iteration was automated and done with a macro that uses Newton's method. A button was created to achieve the PPTD for a specific boiler outlet temperature for the exhaust gas. The calculation shows that the pinch point is located between the economizer and evaporator in the WHRB.

The results for cases 1 and 2 are presented in Figure 26 to show clearly the differences between them. The boiler outlet temperatures that were calculated based on Newton's method are on the y-axis. The figure shows the outlet temperature and the PPTD that was used for the calculation.

Figure 26. PPTD comparison of two cases

The trend in both graphs is growing. In both cases the stack temperature increases about 1.2°C when PPTD increases 1°C. This indicates that the systems are working stably. Case 2 achieves the same PPTD as case 1 but with lower values. Since case 2 has a higher TIT and lower stack temperatures, a higher efficiency can be reached for the system. The information can be used to form a graph to show the pinch point in the WHRB. Figure 27 presents case 1 and Figure 28 presents case 2.

Boundary values for the boiler calculation is set. The temperature difference in the hot end is chosen to be 30°C which is based on the information from the project. This brings the degree of superheating to about 100 °C. The temperature difference between exhaust gas inlet temperature and steam outlet temperature also links to the sizing of the boiler

equipment. With smaller temperature differences the size of superheater is expected to grow which isn't the ideal solution on marine vessel application.

Figure 27. Heat rate of water and exhaust gas for case 1

Figure 28. Heat rate of water and exhaust gas for case 2

The stages in both figures are clear, starting with economizer, then the evaporator and at the end the superheating phase of the steam. The pinch point temperature difference is 5.00 °C. Exhaust gas graph is a linear line as is should be. When comparing the results it's seen that while the same PPTD value is achieved, in case 2 it is achieved with higher exhaust gas inlet temperature and lower exhaust gas outlet temperature. This means that more heat is recovered in this case.

7.3. Heat transfer areas

Pinch point temperature difference is an important parameter since it is linked to multiple other values. One parameter that PPTD determines is the size of the heat transfer area. The WHRB has three major components: economizer, evaporator and superheater. As stated before, the smaller the PPTD is, the bigger the heat transfer area needs to be to achieve the correct heat conversion between recovered and working fluid.

The steam inlet values are set values. The inlet temperature is 50 °C and the pressure is 6 bars. Based on these and the pressure losses and mass flow, the parameters in different stages could be calculated. As the temperature difference in the hot end of the boiler is set for 30°C, Figures 29 and 30 show how changing the pinch point temperature difference affects the heat transfer areas of the boiler in both cases.

Figure 29. Heat transfer area dependency over PPTD, case 1

Figure 30. Heat transfer area dependency over PPTD, case 2

The size of the heat transfer areas decrease while PPTD increases. The difference between the two cases isn't big. The biggest change can be seen in the evaporator graph while the superheater's heat transfer area barely changes. Between the first and the last point in the superheater graph there is around 12 m² difference in both cases.

In case 1 the overall heat transfer areas are a bit smaller with the same PPTD than in case 2. The reason behind it is that in case 2 with higher exhaust gas inlet temperature a smaller outlet temperature is reached thus more area is needed to transfer the heat.

By the look of the graph the steepest change in both economizer and evaporator happens with smaller PPTD values. This means that the heat transfer area decreases the quickest in the beginning per 1°C of PPTD increase. For further economic studies of the process this means that the cost of the heat exchanger varies most in the beginning of the graph. The curve is flattening as the PPTD increases and the derivative of the curve doesn't present as big of a difference at the end of the curve versus at the beginning of the curve. The flattening effect is better seen in the curve representing economizer.

7.4. Exhaust gas thermal power

Another value that the pinch point temperature difference adjusts is the heat rate. Heat rate shows how much heat there is for the exhaust gas to give to the steam. With boiler efficiency, the thermal power of the steam can be calculated. In both cases the boiler efficiency is 98 %. The results are based on Equation 12 and 13 and are presented in Figures 31 and 32.

Figure 31. Thermal power dependency on PPTD, case 1

Figure 32. Thermal power dependency on PPTD, case 2

The difference between the cases is noticeable. The higher the PPTD, the lower the thermal power from the exhaust gas to the steam is. This aligns with the expectations since this means that with higher PPTD smaller heat transfer areas are needed in the boiler.

The curves are quite linear, and no bigger fluctuation is occurring between the data points. The thermal drop between each PPTD point is between 16 and 17 kW in case 1. Case 2 shows a slightly smaller thermal drop, between 15 and 16 kW. Based on this, in both cases the heat transfer through the boiler is stable.

7.5. Efficiency

Pinch point temperature difference as well as seawater temperature affect the net electric efficiency of the process. Figures 33 and 34 show the difference between the two seasons and the PPTD's effect on the system that has a WHRS.

Figure 33. Efficiency dependency on PPTD, winter

Figure 34. Efficiency dependency on PPTD, summer

As the two cases are compared some significant changes can be seen between the two seasons. When PPTD increases, efficiency decreases. The graphs aren't completely linear, and some dips are noticeable after 9°C. The difference between the two cases in both figures is almost 1%pt. Seawater temperature has its impact on achieving higher efficiency. As seen, during winter the efficiency tends to be about 0.1%pt better than during summer. Figure 35 is created to show how much it actually affects the system if the WHRS is installed.

Figure 35. Comparison of net electric efficiency

In case 1 the turbine inlet temperature is above 1200 °C and in case 2 it is above 1300 °C. The two cases show clearly that with higher TIT and with the waste heat recovery system, the efficiency increases. As seen in chapter 7.4, more heat is recovered with lower exhaust gas outlet temperature which leads to higher exhaust gas thermal power. This is why the net electricity efficiency is better in case 2.

The impact of pressure ratios change was also studied. With higher pressure ratio, the thermal power increased but the Carnot-efficiency decreased. By increasing the pressure ratio to 13:1, the thermal power increased by 1% and the Carnot-efficiency decreased by 1%. The changing of pressure ratio works in the other direction too. If the pressure ratio is decreased, then the Carnot-efficiency increases but the thermal power decreases. It's also been noted that lower seawater temperature increases Carnot-efficiency.

8. Conclusions

This master's thesis was made under the MARPOWER project and in this work a hydrogen fueled combined cycle gas turbine is studied and the parameters for the cycle are optimized for better utilization. The target is to present alternative fuels for the maritime sector and present their advantages and challenges but focus more on hydrogen that has been chosen to be the fuel for this combined cycle. Even though the new alternative fuels are more in line with the regulations and legislations that EU and IMO have set for the marine sector, the properties between conventional fuels and hydrogen are different and require actions in gas turbine designing.

The literature review gave an overview of the marine propulsion systems as well as the auxiliary devices. Even though ICE is dominating the industry as the most popular propulsion system with fossil fuels, the gas turbine takes over in multiple categories. As emission mitigation is the priority in the field, fossil fuels have to make room for zero-emission ones. This thesis introduced ammonia, hydrogen, methane and methanol as the fuels of the future and their abilities to cut down emissions. Later hydrogen properties were discussed more in detail as it is the fuel in this cycle. These properties bring the need for a different type of combustor system when compared to natural gas usage for example. Research was done to find the state of gas turbines and hydrogen fueled gas turbines in marine vessels. The search resulted in one conclusion: gas turbines are studied, but not widely in marine usage. According to the gas turbines already on commercial use, not many run on 100% hydrogen. If hydrogen is used to fuel a gas turbine, it is mostly in a mix with natural gas.

Among the alternative fuels, hydrogen is dominating the mass energy content but falls to the last place with volumetric energy content. When evaluating the emissions of using hydrogen to fuel a gas turbine, no GHG emissions appear which is beneficial to the environment. However, burning hydrogen produces NO_x emissions. While with ammonia the byproduct of reaction with oxygen is climate neutral N_2 , there is a chance of N_2O , emissions that are harmful GHG emissions. Both methane and methanol create CO_2 emissions.

The thesis met its objectives. The goal for the heat recovery steam generator side was to iteratively find a pinch point temperature so that the exhaust gas outlet temperature from the

boiler can be as low as possible to achieve the maximum heat transfer to the water and to achieve a better thermal output power for the steam. A marco was successfully created in Excel to determine the boiler outlet temperature for the exhaust gas in the waste heat recovery boiler. The cycle was analyzed, and it was shown how the pinch point temperature difference affects the other parameters in both gas turbine and waste heat recovery cycle. The PPTD didn't only affect the exhaust gas boiler outlet temperature but also, the heat transfer area of the waste heat boiler, thermal power of the exhaust gas and the efficiencies of the combined cycle. Both cases showed similar results in the following categories:

- When PPTD increased, the heat transfer areas in the boiler decreased. The biggest change of area happens in the evaporator. The most visible difference was seen when the PPTD values were the smallest. The change in the area was the greatest between 5 and 6 °C. Superheater heat transfer area didn't decrease significantly.
- Thermal power decreased as the PPTD increases. This was expected since a smaller heat transfer area doesn't let the heat convey from exhaust gas to the steam side as effectively.
- Adding a WHRS increased the efficiency. The efficiency decreased when PPTD increased. When seawater works as the cooling fluid the temperature of it affects the efficiency of the process also.

When comparing the two cases that were analyzed in this thesis, case 2 that had a turbine inlet temperature above 1300°C achieved lower exhaust gas temperatures with the same PPTD values than in the case 1. This means that the heat transfer is better in case 2. The net electric efficiency of the system benefits from WHRS and case 2 offers higher efficiency whether the WHRS is added or not. The benefits were more visible when comparing the cycles with WHRS: case 2 had over 4%pt higher efficiency.

On top of PPTD, seawater temperature affected greatly the efficiency of the process. If the temperature of the cooling fluid increased greatly it would have very negative effects on the process. The used temperatures of 1°C and 17°C are measured from the northern part of the world, so the temperatures will increase while the working area of the vessel moves more south. As the temperature of the seawater can vary depending on the location as well as on the time of the year, it can bring out new questions on will the air be cooled down enough for the next compressor stage.

As this thesis contributes to the design of a more sustainable energy system for the marine sector, it comes with limitations since PPTD is a techno-economical parameter. The best possible PPTD can be chosen after economic feasibility calculations are done. After achieving this, more accurate design of the process can be achieved.

References

- ABB n.d. Waste heat recovery system. Available: <https://new.abb.com/marine/systems-and-solutions/electric-solutions/waste-heat-recovery>
- Alkhaledi, A. et al. 2022. Techno environmental assessment of Flettner rotor as assistance propulsion system for LH₂ tanker ship fuelled by hydrogen. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*. 55, 102935. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102935>
- Amirouche, F. et al. 2024. Investigating the effect of using hydrogen as fuel on gas turbine performance operating under lean conditions at the Hassi R'mel gas site. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 140, 1095-1110. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.09.237>
- Ammar, N.R. & Alshammari, N. F. S. H. 2018. Overview of the Green Hydrogen Applications in Marine Power Plants Onboard Ships. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*. 6. Available: <http://ijmcr.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Paper1384-89.pdf>
- Annex 15. 2023 IMO STRATEGY ON REDUCTION OF GHG EMISSIONS FROM SHIPS. Available: <https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/OurWork/Environment/Documents/annex/MEPC%2080/Annex%2015.pdf>
- Aurelia Turbines. 2021. Aurelia Turbines ja vety. [Cited 15.1.2024]. Available: <https://aureliaturbines.com/fact-sheets/aurelia-turbines-ja-vety>
- Baldi, F. et al. 2022. The shipping industry and the climate. Andersson, K. *Sustainable Energy Systems on Ships- Novel Technologies for Low Carbon Shipping*. 6-81. Elsevier: Charlotte Cockle. Available: ISBN: 970-0-12-824471-5
- Barsi et al. 2024. Marine Applications and Design of High-Efficiency Small-Scale Gas Turbines. *Designs* 2024, 8(4), 66. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/designs8040066>
- Beck, D. S. & Wilson, D. G. 1999. *Gas Turbine Regenerators*. 55. New York: Chapman & Hall. Available: DOI:10.1007/978-1-4613-1209-3

- Bhatia, A. n.d. Improving Energy Efficiency of Boiler Systems. Available: <https://www.cedengineering.com/userfiles/M06-022%20-%20Improving%20Energy%20Efficiency%20of%20Boiler%20Systems%20-%20US.pdf>
- Boyce, M. 2011. Gas Turbine Engineering Handbook (3rd Edition). 387. The United States of America: Gulf Professional Publishing. Available: ISBN 0-88415-732-6
- Boyce, M. 2012. Gas Turbine Engineering Handbook (4th Edition). 51-81. The United States of America: Gulf Professional Publishing. Available: ISBN 0-88415-732-6
- Candelaresi, D. & Spazzafumo, G. 2021. How to Speed Up a Hydrogen Economy. 1-15. Power to Fuel. 2021, 1-15. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-822813-5.00005-9>
- Cecere, D. et al. 2023. Gas Turbine Combustion Technologies for Hydrogen Blends. Energies 2023, 16(19), 6829. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16196829>
- Cha, H. H. 2024. Life cycle assessment of power-to-methane and renewable methane production technologies. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. 206, 114856. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114856>
- Choe, C. et al. 2023. Mitigating climate change for negative CO₂ emission via syngas methanation: Techno-economic and life-cycle assessments of renewable methane production. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. 185, 113628. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113628>
- Deng, S. & Mi, Z. 2023. A review on carbon emissions of global shipping. *Mar Dev* 1, 4 (2023). Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44312-023-00001-2>
- Díaz-Secades, L. A. et al. 2023. Waste heat recovery system for marine engines optimized through a preference learning rank function embedded into a Bayesian optimizer. *Ocean Engineering*. 281, 114747. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.114747>
- DLR. 2024. Retrofit for commercial micro gas turbines successfully tested. Available: <https://www.dlr.de/en/latest/news/2024/retrofit-for-commercial-micro-gas-turbines-successfully-tested>
- Donev, J.M.K.C. et al. 2024. Energy Education. Available: <https://energyeducation.ca>

- Dong, C. et al. 2010. Experimental study on the laminar flame speed of hydrogen/natural gas/air mixtures. *Frontier of Chemical Engineering in China*. 4, 417-422. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11705-010-0515-8>
- El Gohary, M. M. & Ammar, N. R. 2016. Thermodynamic Analysis of Alternative Marine Fuels for Marine Gas Turbine Power Plants. *Journal of Marine Science and Application*. 15, 95-103. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11804-016-1346-x>
- El Gohary, M. M. & Seddiek, I. S. 2016. Utilization of alternative marine fuels for gas turbine power plant onboard ships. *International Journal of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering*. 5, 21-32. Available: <https://doi.org/10.2478/IJNAOE-2013-0115>
- Elkafas, A. G. et al. 2023. Fuel Cell Systems for Maritime: A Review of Research Development, Commercial Products, Applications, and Perspectives. *Processes* 2023, 11(1), 97. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11010097>
- Engineering ToolBox. 2003. Higher Calorific Values of Common Fuels: Reference & Data. Available: https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/fuels-higher-calorific-values-d_169.html
- European Commission. 2023. Maritime transport emissions: Commission welcomes new IMO climate ambition for 2030, 2040 and 2050 and calls to set transition in motion. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_23_3745
- European Commission. 2024. Efficient zero-emissions gas turbine POWER system for MARitime transport. Available: DOI 10.3030/101138341
- European Commission, a. n.d. Reducing emissions from the shipping sector. Available: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/transport/reducing-emissions-shipping-sector_en
- European Commission, b. n.d. Decarbonising maritime transport – FuelEU Maritime. Available: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/maritime/decarbonising-maritime-transport-fueleu-maritime_en
- European Commission, c. n.d. European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA). Available: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/maritime/european-maritime-safety-agency-ems_a_en

European Commission, d. n.d. Biomethane. Available:

https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/bioenergy/biomethane_en

European Maritime Safety Agency. 2022. Update on potential of biofuels in shipping, EMSA, Lisbon. Available:

file:///C:/Users/z084922/Downloads/Ammonia%20as%20fuel%20in%20shipping_rev1_Sept23.pdf

Erixno, O. 2021. Energy management of renewable energy-based combined heat and power systems: A review. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*. 51, 101944. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101944>

Fatsis, A. 2019. Design point analysis of two-shaft gas turbine engines topped by four-port wave rotors for power generation systems. *Propulsion and Power Research*. 8, 183-193. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprr.2019.06.001>

Faqih, M. et al. 2022. Dry-Low Emission Gas Turbine Technology: Recent Trends and Challenges. *Appl. Sci.* 2022, 12(21), 10922. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app122110922>

Finnish Meteorological Institute. 2023. The stratification of the Baltic Sea. Available: <https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/stratification>

Foretich, A et al. 2021. Challenges and opportunities for alternative fuels in the maritime sector. *Maritime Transport Research*. 2, 100033. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.martra.2021.100033>

GE Vernova, 2025. LM2500 aeroderivative gas turbine. Available: <https://www.gevernova.com/gas-power/products/gas-turbines/lm2500>

Giampaolo, T. 2014. Gas Turbine systems Theory. *Gas Turbine Handbook: Principles & Practice* 5th Edition. 45. Portland: CRC Press. Available: ISBN: 9781482228885

Goldmeer, J. & Catillaz, J. Hydrogen for power generation. Available: https://www.gevernova.com/content/dam/gepower-new/global/en_US/downloads/gas-new-site/future-of-energy/hydrogen-for-power-gen-gea34805.pdf

Goswami, D.Y. & Kreith, F. 2017. *Energy Conversion*. 2nd Edition. 219. CRC Press. Available: ISBN:978-1-4665-8482-2

- Green, D. W. & Perry, R. H. 2008. Perry's chemical engineers' handbook 8th Edition. 11-54. McGraw-Hill. Available: ISBN 978-0-07-142294-9
- Hosseini, S. H. et al. 2023. Use of hydrogen in dual fuel diesel engines. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*. 98, 101100. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2023.101100>
- IMO, a. n.d. Introduction to IMO. Available: <https://www.imo.org/en/About/Pages/Default.aspx>
- IMO, b. n.d. UN body adopts climate change strategy for shipping. Available: <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/PressBriefings/Pages/06GHGinitialstrategy.aspx>
- Kim, S. et al. 2024. HEAT TRANSFER ENHANCEMENT FOR GAS TURBINE BLADE INTERNAL COOLING WITH LATTICE STRUCTURED RIB. *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2024*. GT2024-122753
- Le, T. T. et al. 2023. Fueling the future: A comprehensive review of hydrogen energy systems and their challenges. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 54, 791-816. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.08.044>
- Li, J. et al. 2021. Current Status and Prospects of Gas Turbine Technology Application. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 2108 012009. Available: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/2108/1/012009/pdf>
- Li, J. & Li, Y. 2023. Micro gas turbine: Developments, applications, and key technologies on components. *Propulsion and Power Research*. 12, 1-43. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jprr.2023.01.002>
- Mallouppas, G. & Yfantis, E. A. 2021. Decarbonization in Shipping Industry: A Review of Research, Technology Development, and Innovation Proposals. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 2021, 9(4), 415. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9040415>
- MARPOWER. 2025. MARPOWR-Project. Available: <https://marpowerproject.eu/>
- Mathur, A. P. 2024. Eliminating or Handling Very Close Temperature Approach in Sizing a Heat Exchanger. *ASHRAE Journal*. 66, 38-42. Available: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/3121701597?accountid=27292&sourcetype=Scholarly%20Journals>

- Mazloomi, K. & Gomes, C. 2012. Hydrogen as an energy carrier: Prospects and challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 16, 3024-3033. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.02.028>
- Memet, F. & Faitar, C. 2019. A thermodynamic optimization of a gas turbine cycle with a supplementary regenerator. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 591 012094. Available: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1757-899X/591/1/012094/pdf>
- Mitsubishi. 2023. Mitsubishi Power Successfully Operates an Advanced Class Gas Turbine with 30% Hydrogen Fuel Co-Firing at Grid-Connected T-Point 2. Available: <https://www.mhi.com/news/23113001.html>
- Mitsubishi. n.d. H-25 Gas Turbines. Available: <https://solutions.mhi.com/power/decarbonization-technology/h-25-gas-turbines/>
- Mollenhauer, K. & Tschöke, H. 2010. *Handbook of Diesel Engines*. Springer Heidelberg Dordrecht London New York. DOI 10.1007/978-3-540-89083-6
- Motiva. n.d. Energiatehokas lämmönsiirto. Available: https://www.motiva.fi/files/11078/Energiatehokas_lammonsiiirto_opas.pdf
- Placek, M. 2023. Energy density of maritime fuels in 2020, by fuel type. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1279431/energy-density-of-maritime-fuels/>
- Polyak, B. T. 2011. Newton's method and its use in optimization. *European Journal of Operational Research*. 181, 1086-1096. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2005.06.076>
- Poullikkas, A. 2024. An overview of current and future sustainable gas turbine technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 9, 409-443. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2004.05.009>
- Regulation (EU) 2023/1805. 2023. Regulation (EU) 2023/1805 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on the use of renewable and low-carbon fuels in maritime transport, and amending Directive 2009/16/EC. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1805/oj/eng>

Sayma, I. A. 2017. Gas Turbines for Marine Applications. In: Carlton, J., Jukes, P. & Sang, C-Y. (Eds.), Encyclopedia of Maritime and Offshore Engineering. 1-10. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Available: ISBN 9781118476406

Senmatic. n.d. The 5 most relevant marine fuels right now. Available: <https://senmatic.com/knowledge/sensor/the-5-most-relevant-marine-fuels-right-now/>

Siemens. n.d. Reliable gas turbines. Available: <https://www.siemens-energy.com/global/en/home/products-services/product-offerings/gas-turbines.html>

Siemens Energy. 2025. Zero Emission Hydrogen Turbine Center. Available: <https://www.siemens-energy.com/global/en/home/products-services/solutions-usecase/hydrogen/zehtc.html>

Sollai, S. et al. 2022. Renewable methanol production from green hydrogen and captured CO₂: A techno-economic assessment. Journal of CO₂ Utilization. 68, 102345. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2022.102345>

Statista. 2023. Annual fuel consumption by ships worldwide from 2019 to 2020, by fuel type. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1266963/amount-of-fuel-consumed-by-ships-worldwide-by-fuel-type/>

Statista. 2024. Carbon dioxide emissions from international shipping worldwide from 1970 to 2023. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1291468/international-shipping-emissions-worldwide/>

Theotokatos, G. et al. 2016. Investigation of ship cooling system operation for improving energy efficiency. Journal of Marine Science and Technology. 22, 38-50. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00773-016-0395-9>

Thurman, A. a. 2023. Ammonia as marine fuel? It is easier if you do it smart. Wärtsilä. Available: <https://www.wartsila.com/insights/article/ammonia-fuel-for-thought-in-our-deep-dive>

Thurman, A. b. 2023. Methanol as marine fuel-is it the solution you are looking for? Available: <https://www.wartsila.com/insights/article/methanol-fuel-for-thought-in-our-deep-dive-q-a>

Tingas, E. 2023. Hydrogen Combustion in Gas Turbines. Gkantonas S. et al. Hydrogen for Future Thermal Engines. 409-411. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. Available: ISBN 978-3-031-28411-3

U.S. Department of Energy. n.d. Hydrogen Storage. Available:
<https://www.energy.gov/eere/fuelcells/hydrogen-storage>

Wang, Z. et al. 2023. Analysis and evaluation of fuel cell technologies for sustainable ship power: Energy efficiency and environmental impact. Energy Conversion and Management: X. 21, 100482. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2023.100482>

Wu, S-Y. et al. 2014. Determining the optimal pinch point temperature difference of evaporator for waste heat recovery. Journal of the Energy Institute. 87, 140-151. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joei.2014.03.010>

Wärtsilä, a. 2025. Onboard carbon capture and storage. Available:
<https://www.wartsila.com/marine/products/exhaust-treatment/carbon-capture-and-storage>

Wärtsilä, b. 2025. Future fuels in shipping. Available:
<https://www.wartsila.com/marine/decarbonisation/future-fuels-development>

Xiao, G. et al. 2017. Recuperators for micro gas turbines: A review. Applied Energy. 197, 83-99. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.03.095>

Yang, N. et al. 2023. High pressure hydrogen leakage diffusion: Research progress. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy. 50, 1029-1046. Available:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.08.221>

Yu, C. et al. 2021. Analysis of Water-Cooled Intercooler Thermal Characteristics. Energies 2021, 14(24), 8332. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14248332>

Zhang, T. et al. 2023. Hydrogen liquefaction and storage: Recent progress and perspectives. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. 176, 113204. Available:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113204>

Zuo, W. et al. 2020. Review of flue gas acid dew-point and related low temperature corrosion. Journal of the Energy Institute. 93, 1666-1677. Available:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joei.2020.02.004>

Öberg, S. et al. 2021. Exploring the competitiveness of hydrogen-fueled gas turbines in future energy systems. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*. 47, 624-644. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.10.035>